

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

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QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

The last version has been reviewed by the main partners involved in the work.

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Row	Version	Date	Reviewers	Description
1	V1.0	26/10/2023	EVENOR	Compilation of questionnaires provided by partners and analysis
2	V1.1	30/10/2023	Partners	Minor comments provided
3	V1.2	31/10/2023	EVENOR	FINAL version

Project Consortium

N°	Participant organisation name	Country
1	EVENOR TECH SLU	ES
2	LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG	GE
3	ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA	LV
4	NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY	BU
5	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
6	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	DK
7	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	GE
8	ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES	FR
9	ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL	IT
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	IT
11	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL
12	EESTI TAIMEKASVATUSE INSTITUUT	EE
13	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
14	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	IT
15	ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA	ES
16	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	GB

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1 Summary

This research work file provides a comprehensive **overview of soil health business models**, including definitions and types, challenges and potentialities, and key features such as value chain, collective implementation, payment for ecosystem services, and carbon credits by stakeholders. Soil health business models are a relatively new and emerging field, but they have the potential to play a significant role in improving soil health and providing ecosystem services.

A **stakeholder questionnaire** was conducted to assess the current state of soil health business models and identify opportunities and challenges for their implementation. The questionnaire included different sections dedicated to different topics as identification of main soil health activities carried out, soil health targets, soil threats more relevant, contract type and time preferences and a strength, weakness, opportunities and threats (SWOT) analysis.

Key Findings

- **Soil threats:** The most relevant soil threats identified by stakeholders were acidification and nutrient loss.
- **Soil health business model categories:** The most preferred soil health business model categories were payment for ecosystem services and carbon credits.
- **Existing incentives:** The existing incentives that contribute the most to the implementation of soil health business models were direct payment or reward for ecosystem services, subsidies, and marketing labels within certificates.
- **Barriers to implementation:** The main barriers to implementing soil health business models were lack of information, lack of policies to facilitate their implementation, high upfront costs, and difficulty of measuring and monitoring soil health.
- **Strengths of soil health business models:** The strengths of soil health business models include the know-how of the soils by the people involved in the soil management, the selection of long-term monitoring indicators according to the local attributes, and the improvement of soil health and ecosystem services provided in a sustainable way.
- **Weaknesses of soil health business models:** The weaknesses of soil health business models include the lack of awareness of the benefits of soil health, the high upfront costs of implementation, and the difficulty of measuring and monitoring soil health.
- **Opportunities for soil health business models:** The opportunities for soil health business models include the increasing demand for sustainable and ethical food products, government support for soil health initiatives, and new technologies to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of soil health practices.
- **Threats to soil health business models:** The threats to soil health business models include climate

change, economic instability, and lack of coordination between different stakeholders.

The **findings** of the stakeholder questionnaire suggest that there is a strong **potential** for **soil health business models** to play a role in **improving soil health** and providing **ecosystem services**. However, there are also a number of challenges that need to be addressed in order to facilitate their implementation.

One of the main **challenges** is the **lack of information** about soil health business models. Many land managers and other stakeholders are not aware of the different types of models that exist, the benefits they can offer, and the costs involved. It is important to develop and disseminate educational resources to raise awareness of soil health business models and their potential benefits.

Another challenge is the **lack of policies** to **support** the **implementation** of soil health business models. Governments can play a role in creating a supportive policy environment for soil health businesses by providing financial incentives, removing regulatory barriers, and promoting public-private partnerships.

The high upfront costs of implementing soil health practices can also be a barrier for some land managers. Governments and businesses can help to address this challenge by providing subsidies or other forms of financial assistance to land managers who are interested in implementing soil health practices.

Finally, it is important to develop and implement effective methods for measuring and monitoring soil health. This will help to ensure that soil health is improving over time and that land managers are receiving fair compensation for the ecosystem services they are providing.

Soil health business models have the potential to play a significant role in improving soil health and providing ecosystem services. However, there are several challenges that need to be addressed in order to facilitate their implementation. Governments, businesses, and other stakeholders can all play a role in supporting the development and implementation of successful soil health business models.

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope of Task 1.1

In practice, task 1.1 was implemented through the 2 steps well differentiated. The first step was the development of a baseline framework which contains all the definitions and types of soil health business (including variables related) for a common vocabulary in the project. The fundamental aim of the work in task 1.1 was to gain a deeper understanding of the soil health business models (challenges and potentialities). The first step was conducted by literature review. Based on the feedback received from stakeholders in the second step,

the barriers and needs can be identified to develop useful new soil health business models.

This deliverable gathers the results of the stakeholders questionnaires regarding the key features of soil health business models that the NOVASOIL project has focused on during its activities (namely, value chain, collective implementation, payment for Ecosystem Services and Carbon credits). In addition, the most important strengths, weakness, opportunities and threats factors (SWOT analysis) affecting the adoption of the business models are represented.

2.2 Deliverable outline

In the **third chapter**, the **organisation** and **data collection** of the questionnaires are presented. In addition, a descriptive analysis of the participant distribution is presented.

The **first part** of **chapter 4** deals with the results obtained in general as potential ways to increase the implementation of soil health business models. **The second part** includes the results obtained per country.

Chapter 5 provides a discussion about results obtained.

Chapter 6 presents the **conclusions** and **proposals** for the **next steps** in developing and practical adoption of new soil health business models.

3 Data collection and analysis

3.1 Methodology

The work plan for organising an international questionnaire was presented to the partners in the summer of 2023. More accurate objectives and means to implement the distribution plan of questionnaires were discussed with work package leaders in the monitoring meeting. The guiding document and the first version of the questionnaires were circulated by email in **August of 2023**. Instructions and a draft of the questionnaire were provided by EVENOR. A final version was circulated at the beginning of September based on the feedback provided by the consortium.

All the partners involved in **task 1.1** and **AREFLH** and **ASAJA** implemented their own strategy based on their own experience and the tips provided by EVENOR. The partners acted as facilitators in the questionnaires (**Table 1**). All the partners involved arranged the questionnaire plan at national level except two which plans were conducted at international level.

AREFLH and CNRS collaborated to compile questionnaires from France.

The questionnaires were held between **1st September 2023 – 26th October 2023**. In each country, the aim was to reach between **10-15 participants**. The final number of participants varied from 2 to 15 (Table 1). The aim was to reach stakeholders from different backgrounds, organisations acting at different levels, and stakeholders who are acting in different roles or having different areas of interest.

Besides country-level questionnaires, a common EU-level discussion was arranged for all the consortium during the plenary meeting 22nd and 23rd October.

Partner ID	Partner	Country	Nr. of questionnaires
1	EVENOR	International	13
3	ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA	Latvia	12
4	NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY	Bulgaria	14
5	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France	2
7	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	Germany	12
8	ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONES EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES	European level	15
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	Italy	10
13	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	Spain	10
14	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	Italy	10
15	ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA	Spain	5

3.2 Analysis

At the beginning of the questionnaires, the four main categories of soil health business models and common definitions were presented with the same key characteristics as the **deliverable 1.1 Baseline Framework** (Figure 1). After presenting these four different categories, a first section dedicated to classification can be found.

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/>	30-39 <input type="checkbox"/>	40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/>	60-69 <input type="checkbox"/>	+70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Sector				
Farmers / Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>		Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>		Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>			NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>		
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>		Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities?

Figure 1. First section of the questionnaire

The questionnaires were classified at national level and analysed per categories (country, year range and type of stakeholder) to provide an overview of the results obtained in general and per country within some conclusions.

4 Results

4.1 Whole sample characteristics

The final number of observations presenting a completed questionnaire is 103. The majority of respondents in the sample come from **Spain** (24), followed by **Italy** (21) and **Bulgaria** (14). Countries outside Europe were included in a same category.

Figure 2 shows the share respondents by country.

Figure 2 Participants distribution by countries

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistic related to the information retrieved by Part 1 questions of the questionnaire. The majority of respondents (58%) identify themselves in the male gender, while almost 27% of respondents are between 50 and 59 years old. Mainly, the sample is composed by **farmers** (33%) followed by **researchers** (21%) and **others** 21% which mainly are **farmers' association**. Only the 22% is member of an **environmental association**. While that the 89% answered that they are currently implementing at least one activity related soil health being **crop farming** (26%) the most selected followed by **organic farming** (13%) and **Others** and **Crop consulting** (8 and 7% respectively). Finally, the first soil health target is **Soil Organic Carbon sequestration** (27%) followed by **Soil Biodiversity** and **Soil structure** (26%) and **Nitrogen** (17%). Other soil health targets were cited: **Soil contamination** 4%.

Table 2. Values obtained from different variables

Variable		Count (n=103)
Country	American Samoa	1
	Bulgaria	14
	Chile	2
	Denmark	1
	France	6
	Germany	12
	Greece	5
	Ireland	1
	Italy	21
	Kyrgyzstan	1
	Latvia	12
	Netherlands	1

	Serbia	1
	Spain	24
	United Kingdom	1
Gender	Female	36
	Male	58
	No binary	1
	No answer	5
Age	18-29	15
	30-39	22
	40-49	22
	50-59	28
	60-69	14
	70-	1
	No data	1
Sector	Farmers	45
	Researchers	30
	Policy makers	1
	Industry and supply chain actors	8
	Landowners	14
	NGOs and civil society	7
	Consumers	3
	Others	30
Member of Environmental associations	Yes	24
	No	79
	No answer	0
SHB activities	Crop farming	59
	Livestock farming	16
	Organic farming	30
	Greenhouse operations	6
	Agri-tourism	5
	Beekeeping	8
	Mushroom farming	1
	Herb farming	4
	Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	3
	Farm equipment rental	1
	Crop consulting	16
	Agricultural marketing	11
	Seed production	4
	Fertilizer and soil amendment production	4
	Farm management software	7
	Agricultural financing	10
	Agricultural insurance	3
	Timber production	2
	Forest management	7
	Wood processing	1
	Pulp and paper manufacturing	0
	Woodworking and Craftmanship	0
	Forest recreation	6
	Wildlife management	7
	Forest carbon credits	3
	Other:	19

Soil health target	Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	51
	Soil biodiversity	50
	Nitrogen	32
	Soil structure	50
	Other:	8

In **Section 2** of the stakeholder questionnaire, respondents were asked to express their **perception** and **behaviour** in relation to the main **soil health indicators** used and the most important incentives which can be used in their region. First, they were asked to consider the most relevant **soil threats** and indicators from their perspective to classify the potential soil health target in a future soil health business model. **Figure 3** depicts the ranking of such soil threats, in decreasing order.

Figure 3. Soil threats more relevant for the participants (S.E.= Soil Erosion; S.P.= Soil Pollution; A:= Acidification; N.L.= Nutrient loss; SOC= Decrease/loss Soil Organic Carbon)

Acidification and **nutrient loss** are the most important soil threats in **agriculture** and **forestry** lands.

Among the most preferred soil health business model category, there are differences among countries and type of actors. A global overview can be found in the **figure 4**.

Figure 4. Soil health business models more relevant by the participants

Payment per Ecosystem Services and **Carbon credits** were the most popular by our audience.

On the other hand, the existing **incentives** that **contribute** the most in the **implementation** of soil health business models were ranked within the main **barriers** which may affect in the final implementation. There is a **relationship** between some answers provided in the **incentives** and **barriers** due to the need to improve some **features** to facilitate their **final implementation** (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Incentives selected by the participants

Direct payment or reward for **Ecosystem Services, Subsidies** and **Marketing labels** within **certificates** were the incentives more relevant. On the other hand, **Figure 6** shows the main barriers to implement soil health business models. Highlighting **lack of information** and **lack of policies** to facilitate their implementation as the main barriers.

Figure 6. Main barriers identified by the participants

Finally, participants provided their **opinion** about **existing policies** and their impact on the promotion of soil health business models and the predominant role or not of the private sector in the final implementation. Different responses were collected about existing policies highlighting that **CAP, Eco-schemes** and other **policies** may have different **impacts** on the **promotion** of soil health **business models**.

In **Section 3** of the stakeholder questionnaire, respondents were asked to express their perception about contract features of soil health business models. At the end a **SWOT analysis** was carried out from their personnel point of view about a potential implementation.

Regarding **strengths** were highlighted the **know-how** of the soils by the people involved in the soil management (farmers, forestry management, etc). They know the status of the soil and have knowledge about different **local practices** that can be implemented. As well as, the selection of **long-term** monitoring indicators according to the local attributes. Of course, the improvement of soil health and ecosystem services provided in a sustainable way.

Regarding **weakness** were highlighted the **lack of interest** by some landowners to implement long contracts because their own interest can be change. Several times landowners expect have results fast and this could be

variable in different land uses. As well as, the lack of interest by the **market** in soil health and the final consumer were highlighted too. There is a lack of **information** and knowledge to facilitate the implementation of this kind of business. Finally, a preliminary investment could be required to implement a business model related to the improvement of soil health and for that there is a lack of economic resources.

Regarding **opportunities**, most of participants cited the **new market opportunities** and **incomes** to implement this kind of business models. In addition, the ecosystem services provided like the climate regulation can support to mitigate climate change impacts and improve human and environmental health. Some of participants highlighted the possibility to obtain new products for the market by the implementation of soil health business models.

Finally, regarding **threats**, lack of **consumer interest** and the absence of **official standards** for the recognition of practices that improve soil health were cited. As well as, the products obtained from agricultural soil health business models may have a disadvantage with products from outside Europe cheaper.

4.2 Country-specific focus

4.2.1 Bulgaria

The collection of data from Bulgaria (**n=14**) was conducted by small groups of discussion conducted by NBU.

First meeting: 26/09/2023 in Plovdiv, 2 Misia str., region Plovdiv, representatives of different types of stakeholders participated (land owners, cooperative members, farmers, researchers and consultants). Most of the participants have a dual role (the same participant has two roles as a stakeholder). After an introduction to the project and an introduction to the survey, they began to complete the questionnaire. An interesting discussion ensued after completing the questionnaire. The participants were interested in the topic of strengths and weaknesses, where they exchanged interesting views in relation to question 3.4 and ranking in question 2.1.

Second meeting: 26/09/2023 in meeting room of Hotel Markovo, region Plovdiv, municipality Rhodopes, village of Markovo 4108, locality "Isaka" 44A, a homogeneous group represented by stakeholders who are landowners and agricultural producers (some of them winegrowers). The main discussion with them was on question 2.1 related to the ranking of the different factors.

Third meeting: 27/09/2023 in Tsalapitsa, 1 Stefan Stambolov str., region Plovdiv, a representative of the National Association of Bulgarian Wine growers. He has also a role as the landowner and the farmer/winegrower. The interview with him showed that he has a different opinion about the environmental policy of the European Union, expressing a highly critical opinion.

Fourth meeting: 27/09/2023 in Plovdiv, 67, Sankt Petersburg bul., region Plovdiv involved two representatives of the Regional Executive Wine Agency in Plovdiv, who answered the survey in their role as representatives for the public administration. The main discussion with them underlined the importance of the problem of soil health for Bulgaria and more specifically viticulture and wine production in the Plovdiv region.

Fifth meeting: 28/09/2023 in Brestovitsa, 5 Petrova niva str., region Plovdiv, Lozaro-vinarska kooperacia "Vinarksa izba" included two representatives of wine and vine, they manage the cooperative's hotel and are the chairman and member of a wine and vine cooperative. After completing the questionnaires, it became clear in a discussion that they value very highly the need to cooperate in the value chain.

Sixth meeting: 29/09/2023 in Sofia, 136 Tsar Boris III bul., State Fund Agriculture, a member of the state administration. She is a representative at the national level and noted the importance of policies regarding ecology and soil health. According to her, it is important to have different financial incentives for soil health at the state level, at the EU level and at the local level.

Figure 7. Picture from the first meeting organised by NBU

Regarding the incentives more relevant selected were subsidies (23%) and Direct payment or reward for Ecosystem Services (13%) most voted. Legal prohibitions, Marketing labels within certificates and Green Bonds achieve 11% each one (**Figure 8**).

Figure 8. Incentives distribution voted by Bulgarian participants

The Bulgarian stakeholders identified the main barriers to implement soil health business models in their area. Lack of information, lack of interest by landowners and lack of digitalization are the largest barriers with 17% of the votes. The results obtained show not only one barrier or most relevant (**Figure 9**). Notably, lack of digitalisation of the sector were one of the most voted being the only one country which highlight this barrier.

Figure 9. Main barriers identified for the implementation of soil health business models.

One of the specific questions about the implementation of **soil health business models** is the contract time preferences. This means the **length of**

the contract where the different parts must follow the signed in the agreement without changes no approved (specific land management, use or not some products, etc). In this question, participants musted their opinion about the best length under different land uses.

Figure 10. Contract time preferences selected by the Bulgarian participants

Figure 10 shows a high preference of **20 years** of length for **forestry** land uses meanwhile **5 and 10 years** were the most voted by agriculture lands. Finally, **10 years** followed by **20 years** were selected for **Urban lands**.

Finally, the participants did a **SWOT** exercise from their point of view to the implementation of soil health business models in their location. Following a summary of the main answers received can be found.

Strengths	Weakness
The implementation of a soil health business model may provide an increase of the productivity in long-term due to the friendly practices implemented. As well as, soil sampling could be a part of the monitoring process and then will increase the soil database of our country.	To implement a soil health business model, economic resources will be needed. An initial investment or support will be required to ensure the profitability of the system. As well as, there is a lack of information about practices and parameters to define a soil health or unhealth.
Opportunities	Threats
A new soil health business model could be a new financial tool where producers can increase their own market opportunities.	The main threat is the potential lack of interest by the consumers. The willingness to pay by the consumers must be analysed before to implement the soil health business model.

4.2.2 France

The collections of data related to France, was conducted by **AREFLH** and **CNRS**. For a total number of **8 responses**. An online questionnaire was circulated via email by **AREFLH** meanwhile **CNRS** was via interview. AREFLH distributed the questionnaires to different Organisation of producers and Association of Producers organisation's (farmers). On the other hand, CNRS made interviews to ensure the comprehension of some questions and ensure the quality of the answers.

Figure 11. Incentives more relevant from French participants

Direct payment or reward for Ecosystem Services and **Subsidies** still being the most relevant by the participants (30% and 25%), followed by Marketing labels within certificates (15%). However, **Legal prohibitions** and **Conservation easements** achieve a 10% (Figure 11).

Regarding the **barriers** to implement soil health business (**Figure 12**), **lack of information** about it, **lack of economic resources** and **lack of appreciation** by the **consumers** were the most important selected with 28%, 22% and 22% respectively.

Figure 12. Main barriers selected by the French participants.

Other topic asked were the preferences about contract length in Agriculture, Forestry and Urban sites (**Figure 13**). In Agricultural lands, **5 years** were the selection most voted and **20 years** for Forestry and Urban sites.

Figure 13. Contract length preferences in France.

Regarding **SWOT** exercises, the main items have been summarising in the following table:

Strengths	Weakness
The implementation of a soil health business model will improve soil quality and will provide a new	To implement a soil health business model, economic resources will be needed. An initial investment or

income for farmers and landowners. As well as, it could ensure a long-term commitment in the implementation and will have an active a real contribution to soil health.	support will be required to ensure the profitability of the system. However, administrative constraints can be found so a facilitation of the process is needed. As well as, several times, landowners are not necessary the one who manages so collective implementation type could be needed.
Opportunities	Threats
A new soil health business model could be a new financial tool.	The main threat is the potential lack of interest by the consumers again. As well as there are too many old-world farmers and a lack of interest by landowners so is necessary an effort in these terms.

4.2.3 Germany

The collection of data related to Germany (**n=12**) was conducted by **TUM**. Respondents were contacted by email and participants filled out the electronic version of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was translated to ensure the correct understanding of the questions and compile rich value for the project.

Figure 14. Incentives selected by German participants.

Direct payment or reward for Ecosystem Services and **Marketing labels** within **certificates** were the incentives most selected (22% and 19%) followed by subsidies (14%) (Figure 14).

Figure 15. Barriers identified by German stakeholders.

Lack of information (19%), **lack of appreciation by consumer** (19%) and **lack of economic resources** (19%) were the most frequently voted barriers. Notably, **lack of policies** and **lack of a support agency** obtained low representation as main barriers compared to other countries (Figure 15). The lowest barrier voted was lack of digitalisation of the sector (0%).

Figure 16. Contract length preferences in the implementation of soil health business models under different land uses.

Regarding **contract duration**, there is a high predominant preference with 20 years in Forestry sites meanwhile 5 and 10 were more preferred in Agriculture and Urban sites (**Figure 16**).

Regarding **SWOT** exercises, the main items are summarised in the following table:

Strengths	Weakness
The implementation of a soil health business model must include landowner/farmer because they are who know their land. They can provide their know-how in the final implementation of the soil health business model.	There is a lack on expert advice, especially on economic or market. If the soil health business model includes hard mandatory measures, it will not be easy implemented.
Opportunities	Threats
A new soil health business model could provide new financial incentives and increase social participation.	The main threat is the loss of autonomy to manage their lands due to the market preferences. This could have an impact on C-bond.

4.2.4 Italy

The collection of data from Italy was conducted by **AREFLH** (n=1), **UNIPI** (n=10) and **UNIFE** (n=10). The three participants distributed by email the questionnaires and solve questions and doubts. A previous coordination meeting to ensure no duplicates were carried out.

Figure 17. Incentives more relevant for the Italian stakeholders.

According to the answers compiled from the Italian questionnaires, **Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem services** is the most relevant (27%) followed by **Corporate social responsibility** (14%) and **Marketing labels within certificates** (14%) (Figure 17).

Figure 18. Barriers identified in Italy.

Regarding barriers analysis (Figure 18), **lack of policies** (25%), **lack of information** (20%) and **lack of economic resources** (18%). However **lack of interest** (16%) were selected by some of the participants.

Figure 19. Length contract preferences among land uses from Italian stakeholders.

Italian stakeholders (Figure 19) selected **5 and 10 years** as most preferred for **agricultural** soil health business models. In **urban**, **5 years** were most selected too followed by 20 years. On the other hand, 10 and 20 years were the results obtained for forestry soil health business models.

Strengths	Weakness
The main strength highlighted by the participants were the involvement of landowners in the management decision. In this way, the implementation of soil health business model may improve the soil resilience.	The main weakness is the lack of information and financial support for the implementation. As well as, potential high bureaucracy and market prices related to soil health business could weak the final implementation.
Opportunities	Threats
A new soil health business model could be a new market opportunities and new source of incomes	The main threat is the potential lack of interest by the consumers again and the difficulty to obtain certifying results.

4.2.5 Latvia

ZSA compiled **12 questionnaires** sent by email and clarified some questions by email exchange. Different stakeholder' categories participated in this research work within the following results.

Figure 20. Incentives more relevant from Latvian participants.

Subsidies (25%) and **Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services** (23%) were the incentives more relevant followed by **marketing labels within certificates** (11%) (Figure 20).

Figure 21. Barriers selected by Latvian stakeholders.

Regarding main barriers selected by the participants (**Figure 21**), **lack of economic resources** (28%) and **lack of information** about soil health business model (22%) were the most selected. Notably, **lack of policies** and **lack of appreciation by consumers** (19%).

Figure 22. Contract length preferences on soil health business model.

As previous results, **five years** were predominant for **agriculture** lands, meanwhile **20 years** for **forestry**. However, **1 year** was the option most selected for **urban** sites (**Figure 22**).

Strengths	Weakness
The main strength highlighted by the participants was the support of the EU policies that promote soil health. As well as, the involvement of	The main weakness is the lack of research about impact soil friendly practices on soil health. It is necessary to provide enough

farmers and landowners know well their soils so it will facilitate the final implementation.	information to all the key actors involved in the soil health business models.
Opportunities	Threats
A new soil health business model could diversify household incomes in a sector very critical. As well as, the implementation of this kind of models will ensure the sustainability of soils.	The potential influence of climate change, natural hazards and market trends could be the most important threats. As well as, the potential lack of interest from consumers of change of consumer demands could be critical.

4.2.6 Spain

A total of four partners collaborated to compile information from Spanish stakeholders. EVENOR sent by email questionnaires and solve doubts by email or phone call (n=5). On the contrary, AREFLH used the same approach cited before. They circulated to their own network to farmers and farmers associations and compile a total of 4 questionnaires. UPM and ASAJA did short interviews to facilitate the compilation of answers from stakeholders (n=10 and n=5 respectively). At the end, a total of **24 questionnaires** were compiled from Spain.

Figure 23. Incentives more relevant selected from Spanish stakeholders.

The Spanish stakeholder's group was composed by researchers, farmers, farmers' associations and policy makers mainly. This group selected **Direct payment or reward for Ecosystem services** (26%) and **Subsidies** (17%) as the most relevant incentives from their point of view to implement soil health business models (Figure 20). **Offsets** was selected too with a total of 11% voted received.

Figure 24. Relevance of barriers selected by Spanish participants.

Regarding main barriers to implement soil health business models in Spain, the participants highlighted two main barriers, **Lack of policies** to facilitate their implementation and **lack of appreciation by consumers** (both 25%). Notably **lack of information** (20%) was selected too as other barrier to overcome (Figure 21).

Figure 25. Contract length preferences under different land uses in Spain.

Five length options were explored with the Spanish stakeholders about soil health business on three main land uses. **Five years** was predominant in **Agricultural lands**, meanwhile **20 years** was in **Forestry lands**. On the other hand, **Urban lands** obtained different answers between **1, 5 and 20 years** (Figure 22).

Finally, Spanish stakeholders made a **SWOT** analysis for soil health business model' implementation in Spain. Main answers have been summarised in the following table:

Strengths	Weakness
The main strength highlighted by the participants was the improvement value of their own private assets. It was also highlighted that the involvement of landowners/farmers could provide autonomy and agility in the decision-making of the implementation of soil health business models.	The main weakness highlighted was the short-term costs that will require an initial investment. As well as, there is a lack of policies and specific legislations about soil health that could difficult the final implementation.
Opportunities	Threats
A new soil health business model could be a new market opportunities and new financial tools, increasing the profitability of the system by the farmers/landowners.	The main threat was the potential changes in regulations or preferences what may affect to long-term contract. As well as, final demands from consumers, it is key to ensure the profitability of the model.

4.2.7 Others

Finally, NOVASOIL partners involved in the task compiled data from other countries to have a perception about other stakeholders outside of the main countries targeted. **AREFLH and EVENOR**, following the same approach, sent by email to their own network with the objective to collect information from other countries. The countries collected by each one has been summarised in the following table:

ID	Age	Country	Gender
EVENOR01	30-39	American Samoa	No answer
EVENOR02	60-69	Netherlands	Male
EVENOR04	18-29	Kyrgyzstan	Male
EVENOR05	30-39	United Kingdom	Male
EVENOR06	50-59	Serbia	Female
EVENOR08	50-59	Denmark	Male
EVENOR12	40-49	Chile	Female
EVENOR13	40-49	Chile	Female
AREFLH09	60-69	Greece	Male
AREFLH10	30-39	Greece	Female
AREFLH11	50-59	Ireland	Male
AREFLH12	30-39	Greece	Male
AREFLH13	50-59	Greece	Male
AREFLH14	30-39	Greece	Male

Figure 26. Incentives selected by the external group.

Regarding incentives more relevant for the external group, some differences were found with the targeted countries (Figure 26). **Legal prohibitions** were the most selected (20%), mainly from Greece and other countries. **Green bond** were the second incentives most selected (14%). In this group, **subsidies** incentive was the third incentive selected (12%).

Figure 27. Main barriers identified by the external group.

Three barriers were identified by the external group, with similar results to the countries targeted (Figure 27). **Lack of policies** to facilitate the implementation of soil health business model and **lack of interest by landowners** with both 23% were the most selected. The third one was **lack of information** about it (21%).

Figure 28. Preferences on soil health contract length under different land uses.

The results obtained were in line with the general answers obtained about contract length. In **agriculture** and **urban** lands, **5 years** was the option preferred meanwhile **20 years** was in **forestry** (Figure 28).

Strengths	Weakness
One of the strengths identified was the money saved by the less or non-use of chemicals with a positive impact on soil life and taste of products. As well as, the implementation of this friendly soil management will facilitate the long-term successful land use. The external group highlight the involve farmers and technical expertise as a strength.	One of the weakness identified was the lack of interest by landowners in adopting soil conservation business models. Specially if the first year there may be no profit. As well as, a reduction of the final production due to unfavourable weather conditions. As well as, the lack of information and an inadequate infrastructure to facilitate the implementation were cited.
Opportunities	Threats
One of the opportunities identified was helping overcome the challenge of environmental degradation and mass extinction. In this case, the actors involved in the implementation of this kind of business model would improve their business image and incomes. As well as, due adopting soil conservation business modes, relevant monitor laws what support conservation agriculture may be improved. Finally, actors involved in this kind of business may have access to specific training in relevant forums and participate in new networks.	Depending on the final location of the business model, a poor mechanization or technology could be available for conservation agriculture, specially with a low income in the first years. Of course, a lack of interest by consumers will be one of the main threats in this kind of business model. Finally, climate change and extreme conditions may delay or reduce the products and, consequently, a profit reduction.

5 Discussion

With a total participation of **103** respondents in the questionnaires, the results reveal a set of common themes, but variations among countries are also apparent.

It is worth noting that the realm of business models encompasses several sectors. Significantly more instances of success are found in agricultural environments as opposed to forestry or urban settings. The participant pool is broadly comprised of farmers, researchers, and farmer associations, all of which exert significant influence on the adoption of one system over another.

While diverse **soil health-related activities** were enumerated in the questionnaire developed by the NOVASOIL consortium, **crop farming** and **organic farming** emerged as the primary endeavours associated with soil health. It is well recognized that other functions such as **marketing** and **finance** may play pivotal roles in the implementation of a business model. Consequently, some of the participants actively engage in these roles and have integrated them into sectors that enhance soil health.

Regarding the **soil health indicators** under scrutiny, **no significant disparities** are discernible among the four listed in the questionnaire. Consequently, it is understood that, despite nitrogen lagging slightly behind the other three indicators, it also possesses the potential for improvement in the majority of cases.

Soil is a system threatened by various factors, sometimes as a result of human activity and at other times not. The results obtained demonstrate that **all** the proposed **indicators** and **threats** are **relevant** to the participants, with erosion, acidification, and nutrient loss being the most significant. It is true that global data varies slightly depending on the country, and depending on the exact location, one threat may be more pertinent than another. Nevertheless, the aim of this study is to highlight primary threats in general and, above all, to compile the perspectives of the various stakeholders who may be involved in the implementation of a soil health model.

Based on the information derived from Deliverable 1.1, the Baseline framework, along with the progress made in WP2, four major categories of soil-related business models were defined. The preliminary study took into consideration the types of contracts that provide agro-environmental goods identified in the CONSOLE project (GA-817949) and its deliverables available on the project's website (www.console-project.eu). The developed questionnaires included straightforward definitions to facilitate participant comprehension. Furthermore, it was noted that business models often could be hybrid. The results obtained reflect that payment for ecosystem services is one of the most relevant models, aligning with current policies and an increasingly environmentally conscious market. Additionally, business models related to the value chain were also selected, probably due to their connection

to the market and their ability to meet the needs of both producers and consumers.

From a general perspective, the most relevant incentives for participants were "**Direct payment or reward for Ecosystem Services**," "**Subsidies**," and "**Marketing labels with certificates**." With minor variations in percentages and exceptions in some cases, such trend is observed across all countries. This may be because other incentives can overlap with or be confusing for participants. However, clarifications made afterward reaffirmed the responses in most cases. In future work, incentives will be regrouped with the goal of improving participant completion. Nevertheless, this provides insight into the types of incentives that can be included in a business model, considering that many of them are linked to ensuring the economic and environmental viability of the business model.

The implementation of soil health-related business models is not without its challenges. The seven barriers initially identified were substantiated by the participants, with a consistent emphasis on the lack of information, insufficient resources to facilitate implementation, and a lack of appreciation from the end consumer. While the percentages vary insignificantly among different countries, these barriers are encountered in all the questionnaires. There are scientific papers and reports that provide information on business models and soil health, but often these are not accessible to the end user, or they are presented in overly technical or scientific language. Moreover, while current policies aim to improve soil health, more specific policy measures are required in this regard. Efforts are needed to foster acceptance and interest from the end consumer and landowners for the viability of these business models. All of these barriers are related to the need to ensure the economic performance of these business models since, depending on the activity and practices implemented, the impact on soil health may not be evident in the early years of model implementation. Therefore, it is necessary to develop secure, viable, and appealing business models for the end consumer in the medium or long term.

In relation to policies, participants noted that **current policies are moving in the direction of supporting** systems that enhance soil health. However, there is room for **improvement** in terms of **administrative feasibility**, streamlining **bureaucratic** processes, and **reducing administrative burdens**. Although soil health-related business models can be implemented in various sectors, the agricultural and agroforestry sectors are the most effective due to the tangible products they bring to the market. This **preference** is also reflected in the choices regarding **contract duration**. In **agricultural** systems, a medium duration of around **5 years** with possible **annual monitoring** to ensure correct implementation and an impact on soil health was the most selected option. Similar durations were chosen in **urban** systems, where changes in responsible individuals for **public space management** can affect **continuity**. In these cases, a **medium-term commitment** may be required, along with political and social will. In **forest** systems, where many impacts may take longer to manifest, longer durations, typically between **10 and 20 years**, were

selected. This may be because many soil health-related business models in forest systems focus on inaction or minimal intervention. Other policies, such as the **Natura 2000 network** or areas with high ecological value that restrict activities, also play a role here.

The results obtained from **the SWOT analysis** conducted generally reflect that the involvement of key stakeholders like farmers and landowners can strengthen the implementation of these business models. They can contribute their knowledge of their own soil and provide management practices that are both profitable and beneficial for soil health. However, the lack of specific policies and a high bureaucratic burden can weaken the interest in implementing a business model due to uncertainties regarding the feasibility and the time required. In many cases, an initial investment would be necessary to transition from a system unrelated to soil health to one that promotes it. Therefore, both financial and training resources need to be available to attract key stakeholders for the creation of sustainable business models.

On the other hand, the opportunities are well-defined by the participants. The implementation of such business models can represent a new market entry and fresh financial prospects for improving profitability. They also emphasize that this can lead to access to new networks and contacts for sharing experiences and knowledge, as well as the adoption of new practices. In this way, it is possible to enhance soil sustainability and the sustainability of production in the face of various external threats. These threats, also identified by the participants, are primarily linked to the lack of interest from the end consumer who may not be willing to pay high prices for a product. Additionally, climate change or conflicts can disrupt the market and result in reduced demand for products aligned with soil health. Furthermore, if there are changes in product certification or if these certifications add complexity, especially in years with lower profitability, they could lead to the disappearance of these products.

6 Conclusion

Here are the main conclusions obtained from this work in a more scientific-technical language:

- 1) **Soils** are subject to a range of **threats** that affect them to varying degrees across different territories. It is essential to tailor soil health business models to specific threats that may arise in **different regions**.
- 2) Among the **four business** models considered, the **payment for ecosystem services** model was found to be the most pertinent to our survey participants, followed by the **carbon credits-related** business model. This trend aligns with current policies and the imperative to ensure **economic stability** for the products in the **market**.
- 3) The preferred **incentives** are directly **linked** to the pursuit of **economic stability** in the face of potential adverse conditions and the necessity of an **initial investment**.

- 4) While various **barriers** were identified, the most prominent ones were the lack of **information**, limited **financial resources**, and the **disinterest** of end **consumers**. As such, policies aimed at fostering the implementation of these business models and marketing strategies that pique consumer interest in sustainable soil products are required.
- 5) **Contract durations** and the nature of monitoring and payments may vary depending on the sector in which a soil health-related business model is to be implemented. For **agricultural** and **urban** soils, durations of **five to ten years** were favoured, while approximately **20 years** was preferred for **forest** soils.
- 6) The active **involvement** of **farmers** and **landowners** is vital in the **design** and **implementation** of these business models. They can provide **insights** into the condition and type of soil they possess, as well as **sustainable management practices** that can be implemented.
- 7) However, systems burdened by excessive **bureaucracy** and/or lacking **economic resources** can represent vulnerabilities for these business models. Specific policies addressing the dearth of information and these challenges are therefore necessary.
- 8) The introduction of a **new soil health-based business model** can serve as a **new market** entry and a source of **revenue**. Furthermore, the involved stakeholders can access a **knowledge network** for exchanging experiences and adopting more efficient management practices.
- 9) One of the primary **threats** identified is the **disinterest** of **consumers**. Meeting consumer needs and demands is essential to ensuring the profitability of the system. External factors such as climate change or conflicts can pose a threat to securing demand for sustainable products, whether in their distribution or production.

All the answers received have been compiled in a dataset what will be available at the end of the project in an open repository.

7 Acknowledgment

8 Annexes

Questionnaire for stakeholders

Introduction

The goal of this survey is to collect opinion and comments from stakeholders about main contents of the baseline developed in regards to the implementation and co-design of soil health business models. The survey should be filled up once per stakeholder.

Their answers will be anonymised and your personal data will be protected following the existing data protection legislation.

Following you can find the table with the stakeholder type and their relevance (derived from **D5.5 Dissemination and communication plan**)

Farmers / Landowners	
Role	Main beneficiaries of improved soil health.
Importance	Essential for implementing and testing new soil management practices; provide feedback on feasibility and effectiveness of new tools and techniques.
Benefits	Improved soil health leads to increased productivity and yield, decreased need for inputs, and better environmental outcomes.
Researchers	
Role	Provide scientific expertise and conduct research to support the development of new tools and techniques
Importance	Essential for developing innovative solutions to soil health challenges
Benefits	Opportunity to conduct cutting-edge research, contribute to scientific knowledge, and influence policy and practice
Policy makers	
Role	Set policy frameworks and regulations that shape agricultural practices
Importance	Essential for creating an enabling environment for soil health improvement
Benefits	Improved soil health contributes to sustainable agriculture and environmental goals, which can lead to improved public health, economic benefits, and increased resilience to climate change
Industry and supply chain actors	
Role	Supply inputs, equipment, and services to farmers and influence market demand

Importance	Essential for scaling up and mainstreaming new soil management practices
Benefits	Improved soil health can lead to increased demand for sustainable inputs and practices, new market opportunities, and enhanced reputation and competitiveness
NGOs and civil society	
Role	Advocate for environmental and social goals and represent public interests
Importance	Essential for raising awareness and promoting social and environmental benefits of improved soil health
Benefits	Improved soil health contributes to sustainable and equitable development, which can lead to enhanced social and environmental out-comes and public support for sustainable agriculture
Consumers	
Role	Drive market demand and influence purchasing decisions
Importance	Essential for creating market incentives for sustainable agriculture and soil health improvement
Benefits	Improved soil health can lead to enhanced nutritional and environmental outcomes, increased trust in food systems, and consumer satisfaction

Task 1.1 Initial conceptual framework (D1.2 Report on stakeholder co-construction of soil health business cases)

Glossary:

Business model: framework that outlines how a company operates, creates, delivers, and captures value. We have categorized 4 types of soil health

business model. Anyway, combinations of the big 4 types can be found frequently:

- **Payment for Ecosystem Services:** focused on obtaining direct or indirect benefits from ecosystem services (provided by the area where the model is implemented) through different market methods. All areas of interest that show potential in carbon sequestration services, water provision, erosion, flood control and cultural services are key to carrying out the model and for it to have a positive cost/benefit.
- **Value chain:** value chain types of contracts generally pay farmers in exchange for a particular product derived from environmental requirements attached to a contract for the provision of a private good, assuming that consumers are willing to pay for the public good when paying for the private good. Acceptability and cooperation among stakeholders are key to this type of model.
- **Carbon credits:** a carbon credit or carbon credit is a unit representing one ton of CO₂ equivalent absorbed or avoided in the atmosphere. These can be certified, but Europe is still working on unifying and standardising this section. Areas with ecological restoration potential are potential business models in this area, as large investors see the opportunity to contribute to climate change mitigation by promoting these actions.
- **Collective implementation:** the role of specific actors and the implementation of the model, especially the collaboration of collectives, cooperatives and farmer/farmer associations. The participation of key actors to carry out the provision of goods and services are important for the design of the type of contract in the model.

Soil health: the ability of soil to sustain and improve the biological, chemical, and physical properties that support plant growth and other ecosystem functions

Technologies: Technologies refer to the tools, techniques, and methods used to develop or create goods, services, or systems

Incentives: Incentives are stimuli or rewards offered to people in order to motivate them to perform certain desired actions or behaviours. Incentives can be positive (rewards) or negative (punishments)

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/>	30-39 <input type="checkbox"/>	40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/>	60-69 <input type="checkbox"/>	+70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female	Male	No binary	I prefer not to answer	
	Sector				
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>		Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>		Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>		Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>		NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>		Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					
Value chain					
Carbon credits					
Collective implementation					
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture					
Forestry					
Urban					

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models?

This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Questionnaires received

EVENOR developed an online questionnaire available for the partners to be used if they consider useful.

<https://novasoil-project.eu/index.php/questionnaire-for-stakeholders/>

Following can be found the answers compiled from physical meetings or interviews.

ID: NBU01

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/>	30-39 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/>	60-69 <input type="checkbox"/>	+70 <input type="checkbox"/>	BG	
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>	
Sector					
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>		Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>		Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>		Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>		NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>		Other <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specify: State Agriculture Fund and Payment Agency			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any environmental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for environmental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	

Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	4
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	2
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		

Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	1
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	3
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain			X		
Carbon credits				X	
Collective implementation				X	
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	X
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	X
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

No, because lack of information

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	3
Lack of information about it	1	Lack of interest by landowners	4
Lack of economic resources	2	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	5	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

yes

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes, sector viticulture, fruit growing

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				x	
Forestry					x
Urban			x		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x	x	
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	x		x
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Higher productivity

Higher quality and ecology of the production

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Inadequate infrastructure

Lack of information

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

New financial tools

Innovation in products

And new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Lack of interest from consumers

Less production

ID: NBU02

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	BG	
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?
 yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	x
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	x
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	x
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	5
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	4
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	3
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	1

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain				x	
Carbon credits		x			
Collective implementation					x
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	X
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	x
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

No. Lack of information

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	2	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	5
Lack of information about it	1	Lack of interest by landowners	4
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	3	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes. Because there is funding.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, because the business is made from private sector.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes, viticulture, fruit growing

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				X	
Forestry					x
Urban				X	

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		x
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area		x	
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

They know the business and they can produce more ecological products and to save the environment.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners

in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Lack of information

Not enough funding

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

New market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Lack of interest from consumers

ID: NBU03

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	BG	
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	x
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	x
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	x
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	4
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	5
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	1
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	3
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	2

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					x
Value chain				x	
Carbon credits	x				
Collective implementation					x
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	x
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	x
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	x
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

No, Lack of information

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	1	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	2
Lack of information about it	4	Lack of interest by landowners	5
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	3	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes, because they pay for this

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, because the private sector is the one that makes the business.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes, viticulture, fruit growing

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				x	
Forestry					x
Urban				x	

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x	x	x
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Producing more clean products and services.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Lack of information

Inadequate infrastructure

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and innovation in products

Innovation in products

New market possibilities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Lack of interest from consumers

ID: NBU04

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/>	30-39 <input type="checkbox"/>	40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/>	60-69 <input type="checkbox"/>	+70 <input type="checkbox"/>	BG	
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>	
Sector					
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>		Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>		Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>		Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>		NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>		Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify: Public administration			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other: Executive agency on vine and wine	x

Q1.3 If your answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	x
Soil structure	x
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	3
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	2
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	1
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services			X		
Value chain				X	
Carbon credits			X		
Collective implementation				X	
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	X
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	X
Conservations concessions	X
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

No, lack of information

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	1	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	5
Lack of information about it	2	Lack of interest by landowners	3
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	4
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

yes

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

yes

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				x	
Forestry					x
Urban				x	

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x	x	x
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

soil improvement, better quality production, ecological production

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

lack of information

financial constraints

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

new financial tools

new market opportunities

ecological products

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

The clients do not recognise the problems related with soil health and because of that they cannot see the benefits and potential products.

ID: NBU05

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>	Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>	Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify: Public administration		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other: Executive agency on vine and wine	x

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	x
Soil structure	x
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	1
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	3
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain					X
Carbon credits			X		
Collective implementation					X
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	X
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	X
Conservations concessions	X
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

No. There is no information and they are not relevant.

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	1	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	4
Lack of information about it	5	Lack of interest by landowners	3
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	2
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

yes

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

yes

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				x	
Forestry					x
Urban			x		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x	x	x
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Improving the quality and the ecologically clean products.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Lack of information

Financial constraints

Inadequate infrastructure

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

The land owners are interested but they have conservative thinking and behaviour and lack of education.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

The great part of the customers cannot see the benefits of application soil health business models.

ID: NBU06

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>	Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>	Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	x
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production (vine production)	x
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	x
Soil structure	x
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	5
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	3
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services	x				
Value chain	x				
Carbon credits	x				
Collective implementation	x				
Other (please, specify)					

Wide range of state/municipal laboratories for ecological control. The analysis have to be free. The results to be obligatory for trading the products.

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	x
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	x
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	x
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	x
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

yes

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	3	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	4
Lack of information about it	5	Lack of interest by landowners	2
Lack of economic resources	1	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No. the Brussel terminology is too unclear and not relevant for Bulgaria.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

No. the private sector is subject to the market and in this sense rational and disinterested. Such responsibility is too much for him beside all other responsibilities.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes. Crop production can, on a private basis, implement such subsidy-based practices. With perennials, soil maintenance is easiest and most controllable. Many annual plants - vines, raspberries, apples, peaches, kiwis, etc, permanently occupy the garden.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				x	
Forestry					x
Urban					x

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area		x	
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x		x

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

They can help him by advertising and explaining because of his soil activities to sell his products more expensively.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

In the absence of qualifications - everything is not guaranteed as a performance. The lack of education leads to repetition of past practices

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

The owners have to look for new markets from municipality, regions and state.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

The corruption of the control agencies (private or state owned).

ID: NBU07

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/>	30-39 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/>	60-69 <input type="checkbox"/>	+70 <input type="checkbox"/>	BG	
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>	
Sector					
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>		Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>		Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>		Landowners <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>		Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	x
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	x
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	3
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	4
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	5
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services			X		
Value chain				X	
Carbon credits					X
Collective implementation			X		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	X
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	X
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	X
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	4	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	2	Lack of interest by landowners	1
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	5
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	3	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

yes

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes, permanent crops and vegetable production

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry				x	
Urban		x			

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		x
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end		x	

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Registered farmers have access to European programs and have the opportunity to pay attention to soil health

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Lack of information

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

To grow and have more information

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

There is none for now

ID: NBU08

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	x
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	x
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	x
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	3
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				x	
Value chain		x			
Carbon credits		x			
Collective implementation		x			
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	x
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	x
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

no

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	1	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	2	Lack of interest by landowners	3
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	5
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	4	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes. In order to have a motive to continue to take care for the land

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

No. All sectors have to take care for the land from their point of view

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture					x
Forestry					x
Urban				x	

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x	x	x
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Every farmer in his area takes best care in accordance with his capabilities

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

The weaknesses are in the fragmentation of the land and the abdication of the state from the needs of the farmers

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

The opportunities will grow if the farmers have the state support

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

I do not see any

ID: NBU09

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	BG	
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)? **None of this**

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	x
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	3
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	5
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	1
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	2
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	4

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain		X			
Carbon credits				X	
Collective implementation			X		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	X
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	X
Conservations concessions	X
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

yes

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	4	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	3	Lack of interest by landowners	5
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	2
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	1	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes, definitely they encourage soil health, which is very necessary.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes. The majority are private sector

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Crop protection

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry			x		
Urban				x	

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x	x	x
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Landowners will be aware of the business models and how to implement them

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

lack of information

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

They have the opportunity to implement projects and spread the word about the need to protect soil health.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

I am not sure if there are any

ID: NBU10

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	BG	
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>	Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	x
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	x
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	x
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	x
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	x
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other: crop rotation	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	4
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	1
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain		X			
Carbon credits				X	
Collective implementation		X			
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	X
Green bonds	X
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Maybe

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	2
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	1	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

No,

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry				x	
Urban					x

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x	x	
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	x	x	x
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Crop rotation

Consultation about crop protection, fertilizing, herbology,

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners

in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

they do not observe crop rotation, fertilize and carry out plant protection that has no scientific roots

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

Land ownership

duration of the lease contract

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Lack of interest or lack of information

Lack of interest from the farmer

ID: NBU11

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>	Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>	Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify: cooperative member		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	x
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	X
Crop consulting	x
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	x
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	4
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	1
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	5
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				x	
Value chain		X			
Carbon credits		X			
Collective implementation		x			
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	x
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	X
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	x
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

no

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	1	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	4
Lack of information about it	5	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	3	Lack of a support agency	2
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

yes

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

yes

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry					
Urban					

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x		

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

lack of information, financial constraints

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

lack of interest from consumers

ID: NBU12

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/> Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify: consultant			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	x
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	x
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					x
Value chain		x			
Carbon credits		x			
Collective implementation		x			
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

yes

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	2
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	1
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

no

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes - the care of the farmer is greater

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes. All farmers can do more.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture					x
Forestry					
Urban					

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

The care of the farmer is essential to the final goal

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

absence of the state from supporting the farmer

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

В момента не са много зависими от държавата и нейната абдикация

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

This is a new beginning, which must continue in order to improve soil maintenance in Bulgaria

ID: NBU13

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	BG	
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify: Cooperative chairman <input type="checkbox"/>			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	x
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	x
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	x
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other: soil samples and research	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	3

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				x	
Value chain					x
Carbon credits		x			
Collective implementation		x			
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	x
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	x
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Maybe

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	5
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	3
Lack of economic resources	1	Lack of a support agency	4
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	2	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

yes

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

yes

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry				x	
Urban					x

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Taking soil samples,

Examination of the content of N, C, carbons

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

lack of information, financial constraints

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

innovation in products

bioproduction on the market

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

lack of interest from consumers. But the level of interests is increasing

ID: NBU14

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	x
Organic farming	x
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	x
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	x
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	x
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	3
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				x	
Value chain		x			
Carbon credits		x			
Collective implementation				x	
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	x
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	x
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	x
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

no

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	1	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	3
Lack of information about it	5	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	4	Lack of a support agency	2
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

yes

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

yes

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				x	
Forestry					
Urban					

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

the gradual introduction of these models

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

new financial tools

new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

lack of interest from consumers

ID: AREFLH01

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specify: Organisation of producers			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Livestock farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organic farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Greenhouse operations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agri-tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beekeeping	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mushroom farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herb farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm equipment rental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crop consulting	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural marketing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Seed production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural financing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural insurance	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timber production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wood processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pulp and paper manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Woodworking and Craftmanship	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest recreation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil Biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nitrogen	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil structure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Other:	
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2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	YES/5
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	NON
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	NON
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	NON
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	NON
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	NON
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	NON
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	NON
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	NON
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	NON
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	NON
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	OUI/5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services		X			
Value chain			X		
Carbon credits					X
Collective implementation					X
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	X
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	X	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	X	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	X	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	X	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

NO! Europe, and France in particular, wants to set an example on the world stage, and is taking the risk of no longer being in the race to produce. In this globalised economy, subsidies will not be enough! After the destruction of industry, the destruction of European agriculture is well under way. These policies, initiated by non-farmers, are a recipe for failure.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

What do you expect from this question?

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

What sectors are you thinking of?

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture					X
Forestry					X
Urban					X

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			X
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			X
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part	X		
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	X		

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Long-term commitment

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners

in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Lack of resources to improve soil health at a cost that is economically viable in the long term.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

I don't know

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Lack of consumer recognition.

ID: AREFLH02

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	FRANCE	
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	Oui/4
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	0
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	0
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	0
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	0
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	0
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	Yes/4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	Yes/4
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	Yes/4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	Yes4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	Yes/5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					X
Value chain					X
Carbon credits				X	
Collective implementation					X
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Yes

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	x
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	x	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, economic operators must support farmers in implementing business models

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry					
Urban					

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x		

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

ID: AREFLH03

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country:	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	France	
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>	Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>	Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Livestock farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organic farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Greenhouse operations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agri-tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beekeeping	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mushroom farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herb farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm equipment rental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crop consulting	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural marketing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Seed production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural financing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural insurance	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timber production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wood processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pulp and paper manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Woodworking and Craftmanship	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest recreation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil Biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nitrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>
Soil structure	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	Yes/4
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	Non/0
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	Non/0
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	Non/0
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	Non/0
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	Yes/4
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	Yes/4
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	Yes/4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	Yes/4
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	Yes/4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	Yes/4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	Yes/4

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain				X	
Carbon credits			X		
Collective implementation					X
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Maybe

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	x	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	x	Lack of a support agency	x
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	x	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No, because it is based on the constraint and not the solution. Agriculture must be promoted as a resilience solution and not simply as a constraint.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, to offer something other than the public "constraint" aspect and to allow investment.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

--

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture		x			
Forestry			x		
Urban			x		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			x
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part		x	
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			x

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

ID: AREFLH04

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country:	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	France	
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>	Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Landowners <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?
 yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil Biodiversity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	Yes/5
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	Yes/3
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	Yes/3
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	Yes/3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	Yes/3
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	Non/0
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	Non/0
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	Yes/4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	Yes/4
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	Yes/4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	Yes/3
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	Yes/5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					X
Value chain				X	
Carbon credits					X
Collective implementation					X
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	X
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	X
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Non

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	x	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	x	Lack of interest by landowners	x
Lack of economic resources	x	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No. The free market runs counter to a proactive policy of soil protection. It always costs less to destroy than to build. So if taxes do not disadvantage the economy of those who destroy, those who build cannot survive. Compare Spanish and French practices, for example. Consumers will in fact buy Spanish products whose producers violently destroy their soils.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, in principle. But the reality of the market economy and the lack of training and sense of responsibility among buyers/consumers will not allow those who do well to withstand the competition from those who do not take care of the soil and the entire production chain over the long term.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

I don't see who stands to gain in the long term. A considerable research effort needs to be made to identify and quantify all the short, medium and long-term benefits of sound soil management (soil itself, vegetation growing on it, the biotope that develops there, the resulting surface and underground hydrology, the impact on local temperatures, etc). The results must then be widely explained and disseminated to journalists, economic partners, the general public, public service managers and elected representatives at all levels (national, regional, etc.).

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry				x	
Urban			x		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			x
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end		x	

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Active and real contribution to increasing

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners

in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

They may not always make the best choices in terms of quality and/or intensity of results. Hence the importance of training and disseminating the results of both research and feedback from those who have invested in positive, constructive methods. But above all, in an economic market that is not proactive, they run the all-too-serious risk of losing competitiveness, and therefore income in the long term, and therefore the sustainability of their approach.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

It is the duty of the public authorities who manage the use of our taxes, and of the professional organisations, to make all these owners known, to explain their contribution to the public good (see Q 3.3), to cite them as examples and therefore, obviously, to give them the financial support they deserve. Without money, nobody does anything.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

When I look at the countryside around me, there are still far too many fields 'massacred' by old-world farmers. The effects of their practices are catastrophic. But nobody seems to know how to reason with them. If their capacity to invest and appropriate land is anything to go by, they're probably making more money from it.

Some feedback:

I hope that the feedback from your readers will be varied and enriching for you, and that you will then be inspired to publicise good practice and mobilise public funding for it. I wish you every success.

ID: CNRS01

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	France	
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>	Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>	Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?
 yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	X
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	X
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	3
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	2
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	1
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	1
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	2
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					X
Value chain			X		
Carbon credits				X	
Collective implementation					X
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	X
Conservation easements	X
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

N

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	X	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Perhaps eco-scheme

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes because it's in a question of culture and could develop a logic of requests and needs.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Y- Carbon sequestration because carbon compensation already exists.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture					X
Forestry					X
Urban					X

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

I am not a landowner and I can't think for him

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

A better quality of their soil if the practices chosen are appropriate + a source of income

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners

in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

To be face with a lot of administrative constraints and Inconsistency between the practices chosen, perhaps the most profitable but not the best suited to improving soil quality.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

A new financial tool.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

To find an interested company and with a long term perspective.

Other:	
--------	--

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	4
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	1
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	1
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	2
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	1

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					X
Value chain		X			
Carbon credits					X
Collective implementation			X		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

N

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	X	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	X	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	X	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Not yet or not really

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes because it's a they have more money than public sector-

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Y- Carbon sequestration because we could have a growing demand from the private sector.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			X		
Forestry			Don't know		
Urban			Don't know		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	X	Don't know	Don't know
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

perhaps a source of income

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

The landowner is not necessarily the one who manages the land, how can he force a farmer to participate in the business model?

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

To develop a new activity and a new source of financing for their land.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Be sure that farmers will be agree to go towards this direction.

ID: TUM01

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Germany
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

Yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	X
Greenhouse operations	X
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	X
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	X

Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other: Offering carbon credits from carbon farming	X

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	X
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		

Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	4
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	4
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	4
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	2

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain		X			
Carbon credits					X
Collective implementation			X		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	X
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	X
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	X
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	X	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	X	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Y: Setting guardrails and targets provides a framework for stakeholders; --- for a mix of action-based and results-oriented action

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Y: Private initiatives are less opportunistically driven and more stable than short-lived programmes dominated by religious policy. When the policy framework is conducive and clear, private partnerships are more effective.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Y: Private actors who work close to the customer with their products and their development and/or whose success is strongly influenced by their social and environmentally conscious image (contemporary, responsible, future-oriented, innovative, climate-friendly, successful)

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				X	
Forestry				X	
Urban			X		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	X		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			X
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	X	X	

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Creativity and innovation on the part of landowners are great. They are mobilized by result-oriented specifications and testing options and lead to efficient, adapted methods. However,

their implementation and review also requires a high level of technical know-how on the part of inspectors.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

lack of expert advice on the economic and targeted implementation of soil protection measures; economic risks resulting from changes in practices and markets (e.g. barriers to adaptation of established practices and crop rotations); Underfunding of adaptation costs

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Financial incentives and social participation by society/business offer opportunities for – often already self-identified deficiencies – economic risks of improved soil management are mitigated, programs often come with accompanying, professional advice thereby promoting operational innovation and successful implementation.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

loss of autonomy; In contrast to "regular" markets, markets driven by social and political values and sentiments are more vulnerable and less reliable.

ID: TUM02

1) General

Age	18-29 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Germany
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	X
Organic farming	X
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	X
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	

Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If your answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	X
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		

Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	4
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	4
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	3
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	3
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	2
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	3

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					X
Value chain					X
Carbon credits			X		
Collective implementation		X			
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	X
Conservations concessions	X
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	X	Lack of interest by landowners	X
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	X

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Political measures are primarily only specifications and guidelines

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Sectors that have to do with the soil.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				X	
Forestry					X
Urban			X		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	X		X
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end		X	

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Landowners know their land with its past and cultivation

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Lack of time for implementation

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

An additional source of income and the opportunity to get to know your own soil better.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Landowners may feel restricted and patronized in their freedom to manage the land.

ID: TUM03

1) General

Age	18-29 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Germany
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	

Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other: Research	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	X
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2

Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	1
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	4
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	5
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	5
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	2
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	2

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services			X		
Value chain					X
Carbon credits				X	
Collective implementation			X		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	X
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	X	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

e.g. preservation and protection of permanent grassland. Diversification of crop rotations via GAP measures.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Label for humus enriching (integrated) agriculture to generate price premium.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Agriculture, especially specialized arable farming without integration of animal husbandry.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture					X
Forestry					X
Urban			X		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.		X	
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	X		
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			X
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end		X	

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Integrated farms (arable and livestock), technical know-how, institutional knowledge (label, promotion, etc.).

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

High degree of specialization; optimization of animal numbers on available area with maximum productivity, Lack of technical knowledge, Lack of institutional knowledge.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

Diversification, long-term increased resilience (e.g. drought stress), long-term secured or more stable yields, price premium, e.g. in connection with extensive animal husbandry. Compliance with regulations, e.g. N-leaching.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Short- to medium-term financial losses, lack of C-bond effect

ID: TUM04

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/>	30-39 <input type="checkbox"/>	40-49 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Country	Germany
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/>	60-69 <input type="checkbox"/>	+70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female	Male	No binary	I prefer not to answer	
Sector					
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>					
Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					
Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>					
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>					
Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>					
NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>					
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>					
Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:					

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

Yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	X
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	

Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other: Research	X

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		

Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	5
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	?
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	4
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	?
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	3
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	4
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	4
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	1
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	2
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					X
Value chain					X
Carbon credits		X			
Collective implementation			X		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	X
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

NO

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	X	Lack of interest by landowners	X
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	X	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No (no justification given)

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

No (no justification given)

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes, agriculture.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture					X
Forestry					X
Urban					X

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	X	X	

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Not answered.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Not answered.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

Not answered.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Not answered.

ID: TUM05

1) General

Age	18-29 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Germany
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

Yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	X
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	

Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If your answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	X
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		

Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	3
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	3
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	2
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	3
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	2
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	2

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain					X
Carbon credits				X	
Collective implementation					X
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	X
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	X
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	X
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Maybe

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	X	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No, There is a lot of support in the direction of organic farming, which does not necessarily mean soil health. There are good approaches in organic and conventional farming to increase soil health. The best approaches from both areas should be taken and promoted.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, because many of them are also supposed to implement the business models afterwards. So they need to co-construct these in order to be accepted afterwards.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

No, I think that all sectors still have potential in this area

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			X	X	
Forestry					X
Urban				X	

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			X
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area		X	
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			X
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	X		

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Improvement of soils, new marketing channels, higher yield potential, possibly better protection of the soil against weather extremes

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Risks, Economic Losses, Lack of Experience, Less Freedom of Choice, Higher Bureaucratic Effort, Restrictions

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

Adding value to the land, new marketing channels, cost reductions through subsidies for the measures.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

lack of interest/recognition by consumers, impractical implementation, higher effort, financial risks.

ID: TUM06

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Germany	
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	X
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	

Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If your answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	X
Nitrogen	X
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		

Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	3
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	3
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	4
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	4
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	1
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	1
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	3

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain				X	
Carbon credits	X				
Collective implementation		X			
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	X
Lack of economic resources	X	Lack of a support agency	X
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	X	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No, because only specifications are given, these are made obligatory for the practice and thus the reluctance for additional own performance decreases.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

No, as there are not sufficient options available.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

I can't think of any.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			X		
Forestry					X
Urban		X			

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			X
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	X		
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			X
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end		X	

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Guided improvement of soils and soil health with possible financial compensation.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Mandatory measures that are difficult to implement due to the weather situation and resulting financial disadvantages.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

New marketing opportunities through additional certification feature

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

A considerable additional effort without corresponding appreciation.

ID: TUM07

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/>	30-39 <input type="checkbox"/>	40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/>	60-69 <input type="checkbox"/>	+70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>	
Sector					
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>					
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>					
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:					

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes **no**

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	

Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	X
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other: Hop cultivation	X

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	3
Nutrient loss		

Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	3
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	5
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	5
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	3
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	1
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	3
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	3

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain				X	
Carbon credits				X	
Collective implementation				X	
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	X	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	X	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

I don't know.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes otherwise the implementation will be difficult.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Specialty crops, because this is where more revenue is generated overall, and thus where the interest in functioning soil is greatest.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			X		
Forestry				X	
Urban			X		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	X	X	X
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

They can generate additional income and lay the groundwork in later years to generate higher yields on better soils.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

They are bound by the contracts to a certain extent and are thus restricted in their ability to act. Overall, they are more tightly controlled.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

They may have a higher standing with the public for taking such action.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Envy and rejection from other owners.

Additional bureaucracy

ID: TUM08

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Germany	
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify: Bauernverband (Farmer association)			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	

Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If your answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		

Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	5
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	3
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	3
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	1
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	3
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	2

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain			X		
Carbon credits				X	
Collective implementation			X		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	X
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	X	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes, e.g. through GAEC 7 or KULAP Humus-producing FF.

However, clear legal regulation for e.g. CO2 certificate trading is needed. Otherwise there is a risk of image loss and accusations of greenwashing. Important aspects still unclarified, e.g. whether farmer has to pay back certificate revenues in case of decrease of humus content through no fault of his own, despite measures to build up humus.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Not a dominant one, but an accompanying and complementary one. Private models must be verifiable and controllable by law. Consumer transparency must be maintained.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Especially vegetable production and special crops via labels. This is the best way to pass on the increased production costs to the consumer.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			X		
Forestry					X
Urban			X		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	X	X	X
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Knowledge of their land and region; Practical knowledge for implementation of measures; Local added value

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Possible investments for e.g. mulch seeding, etc.; bureaucratic effort & overview of legal aspects; marketing of services (e.g. emission certificates).

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

Income diversification; better product placement with consumers; land improvement for production.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Consumers unsettled by unclear legal framework (e.g. labeling); high investment costs for e.g. mulch seeding methods; uncertain success of measures.

ID: TUM09

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Germany	
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	

Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other: Research	X

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	X
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		

Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	3
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	3
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	3
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	3
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	1
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	2

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain				X	
Carbon credits			X		
Collective implementation		X			
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	X
Mandatory farm set-asides	X
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	X
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	X	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Current policies are putting more focus on the importance of soil health.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				X	
Forestry					X
Urban				X	

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	X		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end		X	X

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Landowners benefit from improved soil health, especially in the context of climate-smart crop production.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Information mangle, conflicts of interest

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

ID: TUM10

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Country	Germany
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>	Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>	Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

Yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	1
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	2
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	2
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	1
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	1
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	1
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	1
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	1
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	1

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					X
Value chain					X
Carbon credits					X
Collective implementation					X
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	X
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

No.

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	X	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No, there are no specific plans.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, ensures efficient implementation.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes, agriculture has highest potential.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			X		
Forestry			X		
Urban			X		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	X	X	X
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

The strengths are their own interest in soil health.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Weaknesses are that effect of measures are not visible in the short term.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Improves image of land owners by citizens and is worth it.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

That there are not “payouts” of the efforts.

ID: TUM11

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Germany
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

Yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	X
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	X
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	X
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	X
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	X
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	X
Other: Biodiversity	X

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	4
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	4
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	4
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	4
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	4
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	1
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	1
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	1

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					X
Value chain				X	
Carbon credits				X	
Collective implementation					X
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	X
Conservation easements	X
Taxes and charges	X
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Maybe

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	X	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	X	Lack of a support agency	X
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify) Political and regulatory uncertainty	X

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes, Diverse and multi-component crop rotations are promoted

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, political measures are too slow

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes, standardization of carbon credit programmes.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				X	
Forestry				X	
Urban			X		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	X	X	X
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

They have own/private benefits, long-term benefits by better soil fertility.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

High investment costs, uncertainty in the effects.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Gain in prestige, partnerships between society and land owners.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Too many regulations, flexible action according to markets is vanishing.

ID: TUM12

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Germany
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>		
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/> Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

Yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	X
Organic farming	X
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	X
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	X
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	X
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other: Research	X

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	X
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	2
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	2
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	2
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	3
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	3
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	1
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	2
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	1

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					X
Value chain				X	
Carbon credits					X
Collective implementation					X
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	X
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	X
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	X	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	X
Lack of economic resources	X	Lack of a support agency	X
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	X	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No, until now, only abstaining from practices that damage soil is fostered. Measures to restore soil health are missing.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, an important role and can also dominate. But there has to be a secure baseline (a guaranteed minimum level) for soil health, and it should not be left up to the private sector to determine where this lies.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

[no answer]

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			X		
Forestry					X
Urban					X

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	X	X	X
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part	X	X	X
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	X	X	X

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

One's own interest in healthy soil, the basis of the business model. As long as a landowner manages his land himself, he can use experience to adapt the "management recommendations" to his situation and to identify risks better.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners

in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

No time and money to convert business models.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Additional income stream through e.g. climate certificates.

Better marketing of products.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

In the short term, high costs and time requirement for the restructuring/conversión.

ID: ZSA01

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Latvia
Genre	Male		
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/> Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any environmental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for environmental protection?
 yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Livestock farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organic farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Greenhouse operations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agri-tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beekeeping	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mushroom farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herb farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm equipment rental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crop consulting	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural marketing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Seed production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural financing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural insurance	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timber production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wood processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pulp and paper manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Woodworking and Craftmanship	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest recreation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil Biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nitrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>
Soil structure	<input type="checkbox"/>

Other:	
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2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	5
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	3
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	5
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	1
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	4
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	4
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	5
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	2

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					x
Value chain		x			
Carbon credits				x	
Collective implementation	x				
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Yes

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	x
Lack of economic resources	x	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes. More and more farmers and land owners are switching to measures that promote soil health. It must be a combination of different policies and private incentive.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, but only if it the final decision is voluntary for farmers and private actors are giving incentives to farmers and land owners.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

No, all sectors apart from maybe forestry have a good potential. Forestry has a lower potential as it is planted every 60-70 years only.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry					x
Urban		x			

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x	x	x

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

EU policy currently promotes that and also there is a certain level of support from society.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners

in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

There is lack of research on how certain soil friendly practices actually influence the soil health in long term therefore farmers and land owners are not always convinced that they can justify the implementation by economic means.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Soil health practices such as carbon credits can potentially diversify household income, and moderate any other market fluctuations.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

With time, society an EU institutions could lose their high level of support for these kind of practices, therefore land owners and farmers would see fall of support for schemes and practices they have implemented.

ID: ZSA02

1) General

Age	18-29 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Latvia
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/> Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Livestock farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organic farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Greenhouse operations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agri-tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beekeeping	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mushroom farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herb farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm equipment rental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crop consulting	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural marketing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Seed production	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural financing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural insurance	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timber production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wood processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pulp and paper manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Woodworking and Craftmanship	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest recreation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	high
Soil Biodiversity	x
Nitrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>
Soil structure	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	5
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	5
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	3
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	1
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	4
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	4
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	3

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					x
Value chain			x		
Carbon credits				x	
Collective implementation	x				
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	x
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	x
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

yes

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	x	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	x	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	x	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes, because for example the green deal implementations promote soil health.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, because the private sector knows the ins and outs of business models.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

No, everybody has equal options.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry					x
Urban			x		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part	x		
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x	x	x

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Landowners who prioritize soil health are investing in the long-term sustainability of their land. Healthy soils can continue to provide benefits for future generations. As well as soil health practices often reduce the need for synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides. This can result in cost savings for landowners, making their operations more financially sustainable.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Implementing soil health practices effectively requires a learning curve. Landowners may need to acquire new knowledge and skills, and it can take time to master these techniques. In the short term, some soil health practices, such as reduced tillage and cover cropping, may lead to slightly reduced crop yields. This is a concern for landowners who rely on immediate income from their crops.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

Over time, improved soil health can lead to increased crop yields, resulting in higher production and potentially greater profits. Soil health practices can open up opportunities for diversification, such as cover crop seed production, organic farming, or value-added products, which can spread risk and increase income streams.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Transitioning to soil health practices often requires upfront investments in equipment, technology, and infrastructure, which can be financially burdensome for some landowners. Soil health practices can impact pest and weed management strategies, and landowners need to develop new strategies to address these challenges.

ID: ZSA03

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	LV
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input type="checkbox"/>	Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>	Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?
yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	no

Q1.3 If your answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	4
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	4
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	2
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	2
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	4
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	4
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	4
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	4

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					x
Value chain				x	
Carbon credits				x	
Collective implementation				x	
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	x
Taxes and charges	x
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	x
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	x	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	x	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	X	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes. At least in our country minimal tillage is being promoted, for example

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

No, the business model should have also the environmental evaluation, not only economical indicators

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes, demonstration of the best business models

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry			x		
Urban			x		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x	x	
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	x	x	x
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part	x	x	x
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Other:	
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2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	4
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	3
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					X
Value chain		X			
Carbon credits					X
Collective implementation		X			
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	X
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	x	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	x	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	x	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	x	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes. Ecoscheme and agro-environment payments

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

No. Similar measures are needed in the single EU market in order not to distort competitiveness. The food security may be at risk, typically in rich and agriculture not supportive regions

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Regions with perminant graslands

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				x	
Forestry					x
Urban			x		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part	x	x	x
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x	x	

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

The strengths is only in cases where the land owner has an understanding of the soil. Most of the land owners do not understand that the soil is a living organism and it must be fertilizes and treated accordingly. Much more sustainable land management is only possible if the land is owned by the farmers

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

ID: ZSA05

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 X 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female X	Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers X Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?
 yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	X
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	X
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	X
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	3
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	2
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	5
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	4
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	3
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	3
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	3

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					x
Value chain			x		
Carbon credits			x		
Collective implementation			x		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	x
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	x

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

no

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	x	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	xx	Lack of a support agency	x
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	x	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes, eco schemes implemented in the National policy

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

No, as the economical effects come firstly.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Do not know.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				x	
Forestry					x
Urban				x	

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part	x		
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x		

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Farmers and landowners try to find balance between economical efforts and soil health.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners

in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Agriculture education knowledge.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Long term impact on soil health and farm sustainability.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Farm survival due to weather (frosts, dryness, floods), market (war in Ukraine) instability and increasing the costs of the recourses,

ID: ZSA06

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Country	Latvia
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>		
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/>	Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Researchers <input type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>		Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>		Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:	

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?
 yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	
Livestock farming	X
Organic farming	X
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	X
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	3
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	4
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	2
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	3
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	3
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	4
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	3
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	3
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	3
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	3
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	3
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	4

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				X	
Value chain			X		
Carbon credits			X		
Collective implementation				X	
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	X
Offsets	X
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	x
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

yes

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

yes

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes, Organic farming, livestock breeding

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry				x	
Urban			x		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	x		
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

ID: ZSA07

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 x 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Latvija
Genre	Female x	Male	No binary
Sector			
Farmers x			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			
Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no x

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	x
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	x
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	x
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	x
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	x

Other:	x
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2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	3
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	2
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	1
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	2
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	3

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					x
Value chain		x			
Carbon credits			x		
Collective implementation	x				
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	x
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	x

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe) Y

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	x	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	x	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	x	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

N

Something can only be developed if it has been studied how best to do it. There is no comprehensive research on how to improve soil health in the short and long term. Since no specific goals have been set, there is no estimate of how much it might cost, so it is not included in the policies listed above.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

I don't have a comprehensive knowledge of soil health to answer this question

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

I don't have a comprehensive knowledge of soil health to answer this question

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture				x	
Forestry					x
Urban				x	

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x	x	x

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

I cannot answer this question, because none of the proposed 4 business models work in Latvia and have not even been tested. In order to evaluate their advantages, a socio-economic analysis should be carried out first. Unfortunately, such an evaluation has not been done and there is nothing to analyse.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

I cannot answer this question, because none of the proposed 4 business models work in Latvia and have not even been tested. In order to evaluate their advantages, a socio-economic analysis should be carried out first. Unfortunately, such an evaluation has not been done and there is nothing to analyse.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

I cannot answer this question, because none of the proposed 4 business models work in Latvia and have not even been tested. In order to evaluate their advantages, a socio-economic analysis should be carried out first. Unfortunately, such an evaluation has not been done and there is nothing to analyse.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

I cannot answer this question, because none of the proposed 4 business models work in Latvia and have not even been tested. In order to evaluate their advantages, a socio-economic analysis should be carried out first. Unfortunately, such an evaluation has not been done and there is nothing to analyse.

ID: ZSA08

1) General

Age	34	Country	Latvia
Genre	Male		
Sector	NGOs and civil society and Farmers		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	
Wood processing	
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	
Soil structure	x
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	1
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	3
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	3
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	2
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	1
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	1
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	1
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	1

Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	3

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					x
Value chain			x		
Carbon credits			x		
Collective implementation	x				
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	x
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe) Y

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	x	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	x	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	x	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	x	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes, but there is a vast lack of research on the planned and actual impact. Most of the policies are not based on any studies or socioeconomic research, therefore the impact of fast and emotional policies can't predict precise impact on farming sector in the long-term.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, but the decision for the farmers and land-owners must be voluntary and encouraged with effective alternatives.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes – forestry.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry					x
Urban		x			

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x	x	x

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Support from EU.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Lack of research on different practices and their impact on soil health in the long-term. Without real data and economically efficient examples, it is harder to convince farmers and land-owners to change their practices.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Some practices can be partially or fully implemented in order to improve soil health and biodiversity, but the landowners should be motivated to implement these practises.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Due to the current lack of research on how new practices will impact the society, economy and safety, there is an unknown future for the farmers and continuation of local high-quality food provision.

ID: ZSA09

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> x 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Latvia
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> No binary <input type="checkbox"/> I prefer not to answer <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/> Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Livestock farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Organic farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Greenhouse operations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agri-tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beekeeping	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mushroom farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herb farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm equipment rental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crop consulting	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural marketing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Seed production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural financing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural insurance	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timber production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wood processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pulp and paper manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Woodworking and Craftmanship	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest recreation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil Biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nitrogen	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil structure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Other:	
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2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	3
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	2
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	5
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	1
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	5
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	3

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services		X			
Value chain			X		
Carbon credits		X			
Collective implementation			X		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	X
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	X
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	x	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	x
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture	x				
Forestry			x		
Urban		x			

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area		x	
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part	x		
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			x

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

ID: ZSA10

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Latvia
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>	
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/>	Landowners <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NGOs and civil society <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:		

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)? Question should be - in what business activities are you involved.

Crop farming	X
Livestock farming	X
Organic farming	
Greenhouse operations	
Agri-tourism	
Beekeeping	X
Mushroom farming	
Herb farming	
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	
Farm equipment rental	
Crop consulting	X
Agricultural marketing	
Seed production	X
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	
Farm management software	
Agricultural financing	
Agricultural insurance	
Timber production	
Forest management	X
Wood processing	X
Pulp and paper manufacturing	
Woodworking and Craftmanship	
Forest recreation	
Wildlife management	Hunting
Forest carbon credits	
Other:	

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	
Soil Biodiversity	
Nitrogen	X
Soil structure	X
Other:	

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	5
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	5
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	5
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	5
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	1
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	5
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	5
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	5
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	5
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services					
Value chain					
Carbon credits					
Collective implementation					
Other (please, specify)					Education, especially for creators of this questionnaire

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	

Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	
--	--

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Maybe, soils with high biological activity are depleting fast (look at tropical forests) and with depressed biological activity are improving (blacksoil in Ukraine, Russia, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, US prairies).

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	Financial support

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

I am personally against all of above mentioned policies.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

I don't know

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Maybe

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture					
Forestry					
Urban					

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

As landowner, I want to see the best way to increase the value of my land/products.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

The lack of benefits in the starting phase of implementation.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners

can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools, innovation in products and new market opportunities

New market opportunities and access to new financial incomes but it could be different in different countries due to their own conditions.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels. An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Too much investments with no idea about repayment terms, lower yields, lower income. More time to be spent.

ID: ZSA11

4) General

Age	18-29	Country	Latvia
Genre	Female		
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/> Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Livestock farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organic farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Greenhouse operations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Agri-tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beekeeping	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mushroom farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herb farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm equipment rental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crop consulting	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural marketing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Seed production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural financing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural insurance	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timber production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wood processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pulp and paper manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Woodworking and Craftmanship	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest recreation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	<input type="checkbox"/>
Soil Biodiversity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Nitrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>
Soil structure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other: Soil fertility, soil health in the sense of crop pathogens and weed seeds	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	3 (most often not by external factors but from the fact that many agricultural lands in Latvia are quite new and it takes investment and time to recultivate land and increase pH)
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	

All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	
Soil erosion		
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services			x		
Value chain			x		
Carbon credits		x			
Collective implementation			x		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	x
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	x
Conservation easements	

Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	x

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

No

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	x	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify): lack of actual reality, it sounds more like punishment programs for farmers without not going into soil health topics that might be interesting to actual farmers, for instance, improving soil health to increase crop productivity. It won't receive true acceptance/belief from farmers (other landowners) if they don't see that it actually helps them (I am not thinking about extra funding or subsidies but that really this program helps to increase the soil fertility and health in order to get healthier crops and preserve native organisms).	x

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No.

Although some requirements may improve soil health and promote good practices towards soil health, I believe that there is a huge gap between policymakers, farmers, and researchers' understanding of what is good soil health. The first thing to do is a good education and understanding about what is good soil health for all three above-mentioned parties. I think many lack a basic understanding of why that is important and why that is important locally. Policies have to reward the farmer/forester for good work because, at the end of the day, the farmer and forester are the someone who implements that. These kinds of models must be site/field/farm specific because soil and regions are very different.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes.

The private sector is the one that actually and practically works with the soil and the private sector works fast because their living depends on their effectiveness. First of all, it is important to include local soil 'problems' in these models and only later more global issues like carbon sequestration. However, the private sector should consult experts. Also, there should be common rules for the private sector to avoid permissiveness.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes.

I believe that only landowners and businesses that have scientific, practical experience and profiles about soil can implement these models. Preferably, local ones as they may have an understanding of the soils of the specific region. I totally disagree if big corporate companies are involved in these projects.

6) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry				x	
Urban					x

Note: I think that more years are better because soil health improvement does not happen in one day, but I am worried that there might be some contracts that are not very beneficial for landowners.

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			x
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	x	x	x
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			x
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x	x	x

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

- Practical experience
- Knowing their soil – its pros and cons
- They are the implementers

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

- Losing sort of independence over your land
- Financial constraints
- Extra time and energy spent

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

- Getting new knowledge
- Probably improving soil health
- It may help to market the product. But I think today's consumer is not well educated about soil health. We can't ask that when even our experts have a shallow understanding or no understanding of soil and why it's important apart from heavy slogans.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

- Exactly, a lack of interest from consumers or a wrong populist understanding.
- Another thing, in some way landowners lose their independence over the land.
- Bureaucratic requirements without any actual good for the soil and the landowner. It may happen when certain, generalized policies are

pushed or consumer demands something that they do not have an understanding about and that's what wrong or one-sided marketing may cause.

ID: ZSA12

1) General

Age	18-29 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country	Latvia
Genre	Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/> Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?
 yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Livestock farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organic farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Greenhouse operations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agri-tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beekeeping	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mushroom farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herb farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm equipment rental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crop consulting	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural marketing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Seed production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural financing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural insurance	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timber production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest management	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Wood processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pulp and paper manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Woodworking and Craftmanship	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest recreation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil Biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nitrogen	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil structure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	2
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	4
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	1
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	5
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	2
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	2
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	2
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	2
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	5
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	3

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services				x	
Value chain		x			
Carbon credits			x		
Collective implementation		x			
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	X
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	x
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	x

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Maybe

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	X	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	X	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	x	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

Yes, as there are many eco-schemes and other support mechanisms that facilitate and reward farmers for implementing soil-friendly practices.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, because private sector usually tends to find more acceptable deals for farmers, that in the end turns out to be with higher farmers uptake.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Not necessarily, but market for private sector soil health business models is more active in crop farming – different carbon credit schemes for implementing no-till, strip-till or minimal tillage practices.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x	x	X
Forestry				x	X
Urban			x	x	x

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area			
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			X
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x	X	

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Farmers and landowners tend to implement these kind of practices if it is economically viable, although, sometimes they are willing to put up with light losses in name of soil.

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners

in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

There is a lack of understanding among land owners about importance of healthy soils, which does not facilitate higher uptake of soil-friendly practices.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models?

This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

In adopting soil-friendly practices, there could be a motivating incentive among EU and state support measures. Also, market driven market for different incentives when implementing soil-friendly practices is growing.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models?

This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

The main threat is ongoing market fluctuations caused by COVID pandemic and russian invasion of Ukraine, which makes landowners, forestry workers and farmers to abandon all voluntary schemes and focus mainly on survival in these uncertain times.

ID: AREFLH07

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	Country: Spain	
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/> Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specify: Organisations of Producers			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Livestock farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organic farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Greenhouse operations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agri-tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beekeeping	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mushroom farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herb farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm equipment rental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crop consulting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural marketing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Seed production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural financing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural insurance	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timber production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wood processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pulp and paper manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Woodworking and Craftmanship	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest recreation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil Biodiversity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Nitrogen	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil structure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	3
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	4
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	4
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	4
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	1
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	1
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	4
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	4
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	4
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	4
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services			X		
Value chain			X		
Carbon credits			X		
Collective implementation			X		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	X
Property use rights	X
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	X
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	X
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

No

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	x	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	x	Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources	x	Lack of a support agency	x
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society	x	Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No, there is no sound knowledge on the part of farmers.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, because they are actually the ones investing real money.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes, because they are the owners of this land.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry			x		
Urban			x		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x	x	x
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	x	x	x
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			x
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x	x	x

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Being in symbiosis with nature

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Is it really a good business for me? Is it profitable?

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities.

Improve qualifications in certifications, maybe there is someone who appreciates it and all.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

That is of no use at all. We already take care of our soil.

ID: AREFLH06

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Country	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	:Spain	
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specify: Organisation of Producers			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?
 yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Livestock farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organic farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Greenhouse operations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agri-tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beekeeping	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mushroom farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herb farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm equipment rental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crop consulting	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural marketing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Seed production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural financing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural insurance	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timber production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wood processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pulp and paper manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Woodworking and Craftmanship	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest recreation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil Biodiversity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Nitrogen	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil structure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	4
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	4
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	4
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	4
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	4
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	5
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	5
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	5
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	5
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services	x				
Value chain		x			
Carbon credits				x	
Collective implementation			x		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	x
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	x
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	x
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	x
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	x
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

Maybe

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation	x	Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it		Lack of interest by landowners	
Lack of economic resources		Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No. Too much bureaucracy

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

Yes, because they are the ones who know the reality of the farms.

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

Yes. Farmers

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture					x
Forestry					x
Urban					x

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.	x		
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	x		
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part	x		
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end	x		

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

Knowledgeable about the holdings

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Excessive bureaucracy of administrations

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

Bureaucracy

ID: AREFLH05

1) General

Age	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Country:	
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Spain</i>	
Genre	Female <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/>	No binary <input type="checkbox"/>	I prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industry and supply chain actors <input type="checkbox"/> Landowners <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NGOs and civil society <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specify: Producers of Organisations			

Q.1.1 Are you member of any enviromental association (example WWF, others) and/or do you take part in funded actions for enviromental protection?

yes no

Q.1.2 Are you currently implementing any soil health business activities (Mark with an X)?

Crop farming	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Livestock farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organic farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Greenhouse operations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agri-tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beekeeping	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mushroom farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herb farming	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialty crops (i.e. exotic fruits)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm equipment rental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crop consulting	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural marketing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Seed production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fertilizer and soil amendment production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farm management software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural financing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agricultural insurance	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timber production	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wood processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pulp and paper manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Woodworking and Craftmanship	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest recreation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildlife management	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest carbon credits	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q1.3 If you answer was positive, what is your soil health target?

Soil Organic Carbon sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil Biodiversity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Nitrogen	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Soil structure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>

2) Context/Features section

There are three main areas regarding soil health business: agriculture, agroforestry and urban. Each one could have different soil health targets. According to the last European Environmental Agency report, we have compiled the soil health variables targeted.

Q2.1 Please, choose five soil threats more relevant from your perspective in your region (1 most important, 5 less important).

Soil threat	Indicator	Score
Soil organic carbon loss		
Cropland	Falling below optimal Soil Organic Carbon level	4
Nutrient loss		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	5
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	5
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	5
Forest land	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	1
Acidification		
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels (i.e., caused by external factors)	1
Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Aluminium levels	1
Soil pollution		
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals	1
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from organic pollutants	1
Soil erosion		

Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	1
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by wind erosion	1
Soil biodiversity loss		
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	Excedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Excedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	5

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

In the deliverable 1.1, we have categorized 4 types of business models related to soil health in the framework of the NOVASOIL project.

Q2.2 From your perspective, please, indicate their relevance to improve soil health in your region.

Type	Not relevant	Less relevant	Middle	More relevant	Total relevant
Payment per Ecosystem Services			X		
Value chain			X		
Carbon credits					X
Collective implementation			X		
Other (please, specify)					

Q2.3 Which incentives do you believe are the most important for stimulating soil health improving business models? (Please, choose 5)

Subsidies	X
Legal prohibitions	
Property use rights	
Mandatory farm set-asides	
Offsets	
Green bonds	
Direct Payment or reward for Ecosystem Services	X
Corporate social responsibility	
Conservation easements	X
Taxes and charges	
Conservations concessions	X
Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	X
Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	X

Q2.4 Do you consider that in your region there is a great development of business models that promote soil health? (Y/N/Maybe)

No

Q2.5 What do you consider to be the main barrier to implementing business models that promote soil health?

Lack of policies to facilitate their implementation		Lack of digitalisation of the sector	
Lack of information about it	x	Lack of interest by landowners	x
Lack of economic resources	x	Lack of a support agency	
Lack of appreciation by consumer/society		Other (please, specify)	

Q2.6 Do you consider that current policies (CAP, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc) promote the development of new business models that promote soil health? (Y/N) and justify

No, soil health goes far beyond the current promotion of soil health.

Q2.7 Should the private sector have a predominant role in the implementation of business models? (Y/N and why)

No, I believe that the private sector needs technical assistance to achieve this purpose

Q2.8 Are there certain sectors that may have a better potential for the implementation of soil health business models through the private sector? (Y/N) And please explain.

3) Co-construction

Usually, the impacts and changes in the soil tend to be in the medium and long term.

Q3.1 What would you consider the duration of a contract between public administration or private investors and landowners should be within a business model?

	1 year	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
Agriculture			x		
Forestry			x		
Urban			x		

Q3.2 Today, technological development in all sectors allows monitoring in an agile and "low cost" way. If you were the land owner, choose one of the following options in each row:

	Agriculture	Forestry	Urban
Annual monitoring with associated payments received (if any) in a random area of your plot.			
Annual monitoring with associated payments (if any) is always in a previously specified area	x	x	x
Annual monitoring without associated payments to obtain management recommendations by the contracting part			x
One analysis at the beginning of the contract and the other at the end			

In order to design a better strategy to implement soil health business models in your region, please, answer the following questions from your perspective

Q3.3 What are the strengths of landowners when adopting soil health business? This question aims to analyse the internal strengths that landowners can have when adopting soil health business models from business and environmental perspective.

To have authority over the management of its land, over the applications and/or management of its land

Q3.4 What are the weaknesses of landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the weaknesses that landowners in general may face when adopting soil health business models, for example, lack of information, financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, etc.

Technical ignorance of the importance of soil health and inadequate infrastructure.

Q3.5 What are the opportunities for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question examines the opportunities that landowners can face externally when adopting soil health business models. For example, new financial tools , innovation in products and new market opportunities

Soil is the greatest wealth for landowners. Healthy soil is the guarantee of its continuity.

Q3.6 What are the threats for landowners when adopting soil health business models? This question analyses the threats to companies when adopting soil health business models. This question requires information, for example, related to the diffusion of soil health business at national/regional levels . An example of a threat could be the lack of interest from consumers.

The health of a soil should not depend on the interest of consumers. Landowners need to be aware of the need for soil health.

ID: EVENOR11

1) General

Edad	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 x 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	País	España
Genero	Mujer X	Masculino	No binario
Sector			
Agricultores <input type="checkbox"/> Investigadores <input type="checkbox"/> Responsable político <input type="checkbox"/>			
Industria y cadena de valor <input type="checkbox"/> Propietario de tierras <input type="checkbox"/> ONGs y sociedad civil <input type="checkbox"/>			
Consumidores <input type="checkbox"/> Otros x Especificar: cluster innovación			

P.1.1 ¿Es usted miembro de alguna asociación ambiental (por ejemplo, WWF, otros) y/o participa en acciones financiadas para la protección del medio ambiente?

SI No x

P.1.2 ¿Está implementando actualmente alguna actividad comercial de salud del suelo (Marque con una X)?

Cultivo	
Ganadería	
Agricultura biológica	
Operaciones de invernadero	
Agroturismo	
Apicultura	
Cultivo de setas	
Cultivo de hierbas	
Cultivos especiales (es decir, frutas exóticas)	
Alquiler de equipos agrícolas	
Consultoría de cultivos	
Comercialización agrícola	
Producción de semillas	
Producción de fertilizantes y enmiendas al suelo	
Software de gestión agrícola	
Financiación agrícola	
Seguros agrarios	
Producción de madera	
Ordenación forestal	
Procesamiento de madera	
Fabricación de pulpa y papel	
Carpintería y artesanía	
Recreación forestal	
Manejo de vida silvestre	
Créditos de carbono forestal	
Otro:	

P1.3 Si su respuesta fue positiva, ¿cuál es su objetivo de salud del suelo?

Secuestro de carbono orgánico del suelo	
Biodiversidad del suelo	
Nitrógeno	
Estructura del suelo	
Otro:	

2) Características

Hay tres áreas principales relacionadas con el negocio de la salud del suelo: agricultura, agrosilvicultura y urbano. Cada uno podría tener diferentes objetivos de salud del suelo. Según el último informe de la Agencia Europea de Medio Ambiente, hemos recopilado las variables de salud del suelo objetivo.

P2.1 Por favor, elija cinco amenazas del suelo más relevantes desde su perspectiva en su región (1 más importante, 5 menos importante).

Amenaza del suelo	Indicador	Puntuación
Pérdida de carbono orgánico del suelo		
Cultivo	Caída por debajo del nivel óptimo de carbono orgánico del suelo	5
Pérdida de nutrientes		
Agricultura	Sobrepasar los niveles críticos de nitrógeno mineral (tierras agrícolas)	1
Forestal	Limitación del nitrógeno basada en el exceso de la relación Carbono/Nitrógeno	
Agricultura	Caída del fósforo por debajo de los niveles óptimos	4
Forestal	Limitación del fósforo basada en el exceso de la relación Nitrógeno/Fósforo	
Acidificación		
Agricultura	Superación de los niveles críticos de pH (por ejemplo, causada por factores externos)	
Forestal	Superación de los niveles críticos de Aluminio inorgánico	
Contaminación del suelo		
Todos los usos del suelo	Superación de los valores de cribado para el riesgo crítico de metales pesados	
Todos los usos del suelo	Superación de los valores de cribado para el riesgo crítico de contaminantes orgánicos	

Erosión del suelo		
Agricultura	Superación de la tasa real de pérdida de suelo por erosión hídrica	3
Agricultura	Superación de la tasa real de pérdida de suelo por erosión eólica	
Pérdida de biodiversidad del suelo		
Pérdida de biodiversidad del suelo (subindicadores)	Exceder las normas mínimas seguras de conservación de los ecosistemas. Exceso de rangos de operación (OR) para animales y microorganismos específicos del suelo	2

El mercado relacionado con la salud del suelo y los bienes que se pueden obtener de él es muy variado. Este amplio abanico de posibilidades en el mercado dificulta la definición de una situación clara.

En el entregable 1.1, hemos categorizado 4 tipos de modelos de negocio relacionados con la salud del suelo en el marco del proyecto NOVASOIL.

P2.2 Desde su perspectiva, por favor, indique su relevancia para mejorar la salud del suelo en su región.

Tipo	Nada relevante	Menos relevante	Medio	Más relevante	Totalmente relevante
Pago por servicios ecosistémicos				x	
Cadena de valor				x	
Créditos de carbono					x
Implementación colectiva			x		
Otras (Por favor, especificar)					

P2.3 ¿Qué incentivos cree que son los más importantes para estimular la salud del suelo mejorando los modelos de negocio? (Por favor, elija 5)

Subsidios	
Prohibiciones legales	
Derechos de uso de la propiedad	
Retirada obligatoria de tierras de explotación	
Compensaciones	2
Bonos verdes	1
Pago directo o recompensa por servicios ecosistémicos	3
Responsabilidad social corporativa	
Servidumbres de conservación	
Impuestos y cargos	
Concesiones de conservación	4
Etiquetas de comercialización (certificados/normas de sostenibilidad)	5

Etiquetas de comercialización (sin certificados ni normas)	
--	--

P2.4 ¿Considera que en su región hay un gran desarrollo de modelos de negocio que promueven la salud del suelo? (S/N/Tal vez)

Hay algunas iniciativas de entidades privadas pero no hay un mecanismo / marco de regulación avalado por la Administración regional

P2.5 ¿Cuál considera que es la principal barrera para implementar modelos de negocio que promuevan la salud del suelo?

Falta de políticas para facilitar su implementación	1	Falta de digitalización del sector	
Falta de información al respecto	2	Falta de interés por parte de los propietarios	
Falta de recursos económicos	3	Falta de una agencia de apoyo	
Falta de apreciación por parte del consumidor/sociedad		Otro (por favor, especificar)	

P2.6 ¿Considera que las políticas actuales (PAC, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc.) promueven el desarrollo de nuevos modelos de negocio que promueven la salud del suelo? (S/N) y justificar

Las políticas suelen definir metas y métricas, en el caso de la salud del suelo, sin tener conocimiento de Natura 2000, diría que tanto la PAC como Green Deal se centran en establecer pautas para la transición verde, instando los interesados a desarrollar modelos de negocio para alcanzar los objetivos fijados (muchos pasan por medir la salud del suelo).

P2.7 ¿Debería el sector privado tener un papel predominante en la implementación de los modelos de negocio? (S/N y por qué)

La Administración debería definir un marco regulatorio para que el sector privado pueda implementar los modelos de negocio necesarios, convergentes y estándares

P2.8 Existen ciertos sectores que pueden tener un mejor potencial para la implementación de modelos de negocio de salud del suelo a través del sector privado? (S/N) Y por favor explique.

Los cultivos que no reciben pago directo de la PAC, los cultivos de alto valor añadido, los cultivos muy tecnificados son susceptibles de adherirse con más rapidez a modelos de negocios de salud del suelo propuestos por el sector privado, ya que contribuyen con entidades especializadas en la definición de estos modelos.

3) Co-construcción

Por lo general, los impactos y cambios en el suelo tienden a ser a medio y largo plazo por lo que en un modelo de negocio relacionado en salud del suelo, muchos de los impactos suelen tardar varios años en tener efecto.

P3.1 ¿Cuál consideraría que debería ser la duración de un contrato entre la administración pública o inversores privados y propietarios de tierras dentro de un modelo de negocio?

	1 año	2 años	5 años	10 años	20 años
Agricultura			x		
Forestal					
Urbano			x		

No tengo conocimiento de los ciclos vegetativos forestales, pero probablemente sean superiores a los herbáceos por lo que la duración del contrato debería situarse entre 5 y 10 años. Para agricultura y urbano, no parece razonable que la administración tenga cautivo a un productor con un contrato de más de 5 años

P3.2 Hoy en día, el desarrollo tecnológico en todos los sectores permite monitorizar de forma ágil y "low cost". Si usted era el propietario del terreno, elija una de las siguientes opciones en cada fila:

No se contempla añadir a la primera opción, recomendaciones de mejora?

	Agricultura	Forestal	Urbano
Seguimiento anual con los pagos asociados recibidos (si los hubiera) en un área aleatoria de su parcela.	x	x	x
El seguimiento anual con pagos asociados (si los hubiera) se realiza siempre en un área previamente especificada			
Seguimiento anual sin pagos asociados para obtener recomendaciones de gestión por parte contratante			
Un análisis al principio del contrato y el otro al final			

Con el fin de diseñar una mejor estrategia para implementar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo en su región, por favor, responda las siguientes preguntas desde su perspectiva.

P3.3 ¿Cuáles son las fortalezas de los propietarios de tierras al adoptar el negocio de la salud del suelo? Esta pregunta tiene como objetivo analizar las fortalezas internas que los propietarios de tierras pueden tener al adoptar

modelos de negocio de salud del suelo desde una perspectiva empresarial y ambiental.

Adherirse a un modelo de negocio de salud del suelo, debería permitir al productor implantar una monitorización de la salud de su suelo y consecuentemente tomar decisiones estratégicas de gestión y técnicas de manejo que mejore su competitividad y resiliencia

P3.4 ¿Cuáles son las debilidades de los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta examina las debilidades que los propietarios de tierras en general pueden enfrentar al adoptar modelos comerciales de salud del suelo, por ejemplo, falta de información, limitaciones financieras, infraestructura inadecuada, etc..

Mientras no exista un marco regulatorio, los productores se acercarán a entidades privadas ofertante de metodología de mejora de salud del suelo, pero necesitarán de un fuerte convencimiento para adoptarla. La formación y la financiación podrían ser una barrera a la implantación de modelos de negocio.

P3.5 ¿Cuáles son las oportunidades para los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta examina las oportunidades que los propietarios de tierras pueden enfrentar externamente al adoptar modelos de negocios de salud del suelo. Por ejemplo, nuevas herramientas financieras, innovación en productos y nuevas oportunidades de mercado

Es de esperar que la adopción de estos modelos permita mejorar los ingresos y la rentabilidad de las explotaciones, ganar mercado, tecnificar las explotaciones, catalizar la adopción de tecnologías en las mismas.

P3.6 ¿Cuáles son las amenazas para los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta analiza las amenazas para las empresas a la hora de adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo. Esta pregunta requiere información, por ejemplo, relacionada con la difusión de negocios de salud del suelo a nivel nacional / regional. Un ejemplo de amenaza podría ser la falta de interés de los consumidores.

Una amenaza podría ser la implantación de un marco regulatorio no unificado en las distintas regiones nacionales, creando situación de desventaja competitiva para ciertos segmentos/áreas geográficas productivos.

ID: EVENOR09

1) General

Edad	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>	País	España
Genero	Mujer <input type="checkbox"/> Masculino <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No binario <input type="checkbox"/>	Prefiero no responder <input type="checkbox"/>
Sector			
Agricultores <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Investigadores <input type="checkbox"/> Responsible político <input type="checkbox"/> Industria y cadena de valor <input type="checkbox"/> Propietario de tierras <input type="checkbox"/> ONGs y sociedad civil <input type="checkbox"/> Consumidores <input type="checkbox"/> Otros <input type="checkbox"/> Especificar:			

P.1.1 ¿Es usted miembro de alguna asociación ambiental (por ejemplo, WWF, otros) y/o participa en acciones financiadas para la protección del medio ambiente?

SI **No**

P.1.2 ¿Está implementando actualmente alguna actividad comercial de salud del suelo (Marque con una X)?

Cultivo	X
Ganadería	
Agricultura biológica	
Operaciones de invernadero	
Agroturismo	
Apicultura	
Cultivo de setas	
Cultivo de hierbas	
Cultivos especiales (es decir, frutas exóticas)	
Alquiler de equipos agrícolas	
Consultoría de cultivos	
Comercialización agrícola	
Producción de semillas	
Producción de fertilizantes y enmiendas al suelo	
Software de gestión agrícola	
Financiación agrícola	
Seguros agrarios	
Producción de madera	
Ordenación forestal	
Procesamiento de madera	
Fabricación de pulpa y papel	
Carpintería y artesanía	
Recreación forestal	
Manejo de vida silvestre	
Créditos de carbono forestal	
Otro:	

P1.3 Si su respuesta fue positiva, ¿cuál es su objetivo de salud del suelo?

Secuestro de carbono orgánico del suelo	X
Biodiversidad del suelo	X
Nitrógeno	
Estructura del suelo	X
Otro:	

2) Características

Hay tres áreas principales relacionadas con el negocio de la salud del suelo: agricultura, agrosilvicultura y urbano. Cada uno podría tener diferentes objetivos de salud del suelo. Según el último informe de la Agencia Europea de Medio Ambiente, hemos recopilado las variables de salud del suelo objetivo.

P2.1 Por favor, elija cinco amenazas del suelo más relevantes desde su perspectiva en su región (1 más importante, 5 menos importante).

Amenaza del suelo	Indicador	Puntuación
Pérdida de carbono orgánico del suelo		
Cultivo	Caída por debajo del nivel óptimo de carbono orgánico del suelo	5
Pérdida de nutrientes		
Agricultura	Sobrepasar los niveles críticos de nitrógeno mineral (tierras agrícolas)	2
Forestal	Limitación del nitrógeno basada en el exceso de la relación Carbono/Nitrógeno	2
Agricultura	Caída del fósforo por debajo de los niveles óptimos	3
Forestal	Limitación del fósforo basada en el exceso de la relación Nitrógeno/Fósforo	2
Acidificación		
Agricultura	Superación de los niveles críticos de pH (por ejemplo, causada por factores externos)	2
Forestal	Superación de los niveles críticos de Aluminio inorgánico	1
Contaminación del suelo		
Todos los usos del suelo	Superación de los valores de cribado para el riesgo crítico de metales pesados	2
Todos los usos del suelo	Superación de los valores de cribado para el riesgo crítico de contaminantes orgánicos	2

Erosión del suelo		
Agricultura	Superación de la tasa real de pérdida de suelo por erosión hídrica	5
Agricultura	Superación de la tasa real de pérdida de suelo por erosión eólica	5
Pérdida de biodiversidad del suelo		
Pérdida de biodiversidad del suelo (subindicadores)	Exceder las normas mínimas seguras de conservación de los ecosistemas. Exceso de rangos de operación (OR) para animales y microorganismos específicos del suelo	4

El mercado relacionado con la salud del suelo y los bienes que se pueden obtener de él es muy variado. Este amplio abanico de posibilidades en el mercado dificulta la definición de una situación clara.

En el entregable 1.1, hemos categorizado 4 tipos de modelos de negocio relacionados con la salud del suelo en el marco del proyecto NOVASOIL.

P2.2 Desde su perspectiva, por favor, indique su relevancia para mejorar la salud del suelo en su región.

Tipo	Nada relevante	Menos relevante	Medio	Más relevante	Totalmente relevante
Pago por servicios ecosistémicos			X		
Cadena de valor		X			
Créditos de carbono				X	
Implementación colectiva				X	
Otras (Por favor, especificar)					

P2.3 ¿Qué incentivos cree que son los más importantes para estimular la salud del suelo mejorando los modelos de negocio? (Por favor, elija 5)

Subsidios	X
Prohibiciones legales	
Derechos de uso de la propiedad	
Retirada obligatoria de tierras de explotación	
Compensaciones	X
Bonos verdes	
Pago directo o recompensa por servicios ecosistémicos	X
Responsabilidad social corporativa	X
Servidumbres de conservación	
Impuestos y cargos	
Concesiones de conservación	
Etiquetas de comercialización (certificados/normas de sostenibilidad)	X

Etiquetas de comercialización (sin certificados ni normas)	
--	--

P2.4 ¿Considera que en su región hay un gran desarrollo de modelos de negocio que promueven la salud del suelo? (S/N/Tal vez)

P2.5 ¿Cuál considera que es la principal barrera para implementar modelos de negocio que promuevan la salud del suelo?

Falta de políticas para facilitar su implementación		Falta de digitalización del sector	
Falta de información al respecto		Falta de interés por parte de los propietarios	
Falta de recursos económicos		Falta de una agencia de apoyo	
Falta de apreciación por parte del consumidor/sociedad	X	Otro (por favor, especificar)	

P2.6 ¿Considera que las políticas actuales (PAC, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc.) promueven el desarrollo de nuevos modelos de negocio que promueven la salud del suelo? (S/N) y justificar

Por ejemplo, la nueva PAC tiene importantes ayudas a técnicas de agricultura de conservación

P2.7 ¿Debería el sector privado tener un papel predominante en la implementación de los modelos de negocio? (S/N y por qué)

El sector privado es el que gestiona la mayor parte de la tierra, de modo que para que esto sea eficaz tienen que implementarse en la forma de trabajar de las empresas privadas

P2.8 Existen ciertos sectores que pueden tener un mejor potencial para la implementación de modelos de negocio de salud del suelo a través del sector privado? (S/N) Y por favor explique.

Todos los sectores tienen amplio potencial de mejora.

3) Co-construcción

Por lo general, los impactos y cambios en el suelo tienden a ser a medio y largo plazo por lo que en un modelo de negocio relacionado en salud del suelo, muchos de los impactos suelen tardar varios años en tener efecto.

P3.1 ¿Cuál consideraría que debería ser la duración de un contrato entre la administración pública o inversores privados y propietarios de tierras dentro de un modelo de negocio?

	1 año	2 años	5 años	10 años	20 años
Agricultura				X	
Forestal					X
Urbano			X		

P3.2 Hoy en día, el desarrollo tecnológico en todos los sectores permite monitorizar de forma ágil y "low cost". Si usted era el propietario del terreno, elija una de las siguientes opciones en cada fila:

	Agricultura	Forestal	Urbano
Seguimiento anual con los pagos asociados recibidos (si los hubiera) en un área aleatoria de su parcela.		X	
El seguimiento anual con pagos asociados (si los hubiera) se realiza siempre en un área previamente especificada	X		
Seguimiento anual sin pagos asociados para obtener recomendaciones de gestión por parte contratante			
Un análisis al principio del contrato y el otro al final			X

Con el fin de diseñar una mejor estrategia para implementar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo en su región, por favor, responda las siguientes preguntas desde su perspectiva.

P3.3 ¿Cuáles son las fortalezas de los propietarios de tierras al adoptar el negocio de la salud del suelo? Esta pregunta tiene como objetivo analizar las fortalezas internas que los propietarios de tierras pueden tener al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo desde una perspectiva empresarial y ambiental.

Actualmente no hay consciencia de la pérdida de valor que estamos teniendo de uno de los principales activos de la producción, que es el suelo. Un manejo

saludable del suelo mejora la productividad, es más resiliente y ayuda a mitigar el cambio climático.

P3.4 ¿Cuáles son las debilidades de los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta examina las debilidades que los propietarios de tierras en general pueden enfrentar al adoptar modelos comerciales de salud del suelo, por ejemplo, falta de información, limitaciones financieras, infraestructura inadecuada, etc..

Fundamentalmente el desconocimiento. Se tiene una visión del suelo como un elemento pasivo, un simple soporte para la producción, y no como el complejo ecosistema que es. Esto lleva a que no se sea consciente del potencial que tiene y no se den cuenta de las graves consecuencias que tiene un mal manejo.

P3.5 ¿Cuáles son las oportunidades para los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta examina las oportunidades que los propietarios de tierras pueden enfrentar externamente al adoptar modelos de negocios de salud del suelo. Por ejemplo, nuevas herramientas financieras, innovación en productos y nuevas oportunidades de mercado

A nivel global, el manejo sostenible del suelo, puede ser una de las medidas clave para mitigar el cambio climático siendo una de las medidas de mayor impacto en el secuestro de carbono y en la reducción de emisiones de CO₂.

P3.6 ¿Cuáles son las amenazas para los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta analiza las amenazas para las empresas a la hora de adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo. Esta pregunta requiere información, por ejemplo, relacionada con la difusión de negocios de salud del suelo a nivel nacional / regional. Un ejemplo de amenaza podría ser la falta de interés de los consumidores.

La brecha existente entre campo y ciudad hace que sea difícil valorar el esfuerzo que conlleva adoptar este tipo de modelos, aunque con una buena labor de marketing podría mejorarse, tal y como se consiguió con la categoría de productos ecológicos.

ID: EVENOR10

1) General

Edad	40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	País	ESPAÑA
Genero		Masculino	
Sector			
Otros <input type="checkbox"/> Especificar: Administración Agraria Andalucía			

P.1.1 ¿Es usted miembro de alguna asociación ambiental (por ejemplo, WWF, otros) y/o participa en acciones financiadas para la protección del medio ambiente?

No

P.1.2 ¿Está implementando actualmente alguna actividad comercial de salud del suelo (Marque con una X)?

Cultivo	
Ganadería	
Agricultura biológica	
Operaciones de invernadero	
Agroturismo	
Apicultura	
Cultivo de setas	
Cultivo de hierbas	
Cultivos especiales (es decir, frutas exóticas)	
Alquiler de equipos agrícolas	
Consultoría de cultivos	
Comercialización agrícola	
Producción de semillas	
Producción de fertilizantes y enmiendas al suelo	
Software de gestión agrícola	
Financiación agrícola	
Seguros agrarios	
Producción de madera	
Ordenación forestal	
Procesamiento de madera	
Fabricación de pulpa y papel	
Carpintería y artesanía	
Recreación forestal	
Manejo de vida silvestre	
Créditos de carbono forestal	
Otro:	

P1.3 Si su respuesta fue positiva, ¿cuál es su objetivo de salud del suelo?

Secuestro de carbono orgánico del suelo	
Biodiversidad del suelo	
Nitrógeno	
Estructura del suelo	
Otro:	

2) Características

Hay tres áreas principales relacionadas con el negocio de la salud del suelo: agricultura, agrosilvicultura y urbano. Cada uno podría tener diferentes objetivos de salud del suelo. Según el último informe de la Agencia Europea de Medio Ambiente, hemos recopilado las variables de salud del suelo objetivo.

P2.1 Por favor, elija cinco amenazas del suelo más relevantes desde su perspectiva en su región (1 más importante, 5 menos importante).

Amenaza del suelo	Indicador	Puntuación
Pérdida de carbono orgánico del suelo		
Cultivo	Caída por debajo del nivel óptimo de carbono orgánico del suelo	2
Pérdida de nutrientes		
Agricultura	Sobrepasar los niveles críticos de nitrógeno mineral (tierras agrícolas)	3
Forestal	Limitación del nitrógeno basada en el exceso de la relación Carbono/Nitrógeno	3
Agricultura	Caída del fósforo por debajo de los niveles óptimos	3
Forestal	Limitación del fósforo basada en el exceso de la relación Nitrógeno/Fósforo	3
Acidificación		
Agricultura	Superación de los niveles críticos de pH (por ejemplo, causada por factores externos)	5
Forestal	Superación de los niveles críticos de Aluminio inorgánico	4
Contaminación del suelo		
Todos los usos del suelo	Superación de los valores de cribado para el riesgo crítico de metales pesados	4
Todos los usos del suelo	Superación de los valores de cribado para el riesgo crítico de contaminantes orgánicos	4

Erosión del suelo		
Agricultura	Superación de la tasa real de pérdida de suelo por erosión hídrica	1
Agricultura	Superación de la tasa real de pérdida de suelo por erosión eólica	2
Pérdida de biodiversidad del suelo		
Pérdida de biodiversidad del suelo (subindicadores)	Exceder las normas mínimas seguras de conservación de los ecosistemas. Exceso de rangos de operación (OR) para animales y microorganismos específicos del suelo	2

El mercado relacionado con la salud del suelo y los bienes que se pueden obtener de él es muy variado. Este amplio abanico de posibilidades en el mercado dificulta la definición de una situación clara.

En el entregable 1.1, hemos categorizado 4 tipos de modelos de negocio relacionados con la salud del suelo en el marco del proyecto NOVASOIL.

P2.2 Desde su perspectiva, por favor, indique su relevancia para mejorar la salud del suelo en su región.

Tipo	Nada relevante	Menos relevante	Medio	Más relevante	Totalmente relevante
Pago por servicios ecosistémicos				X	
Cadena de valor				X	
Créditos de carbono			X		
Implementación colectiva		X			
Otras: Imposición de impuestos a quien degrada la salud de los suelos				X	

P2.3 ¿Qué incentivos cree que son los más importantes para estimular la salud del suelo mejorando los modelos de negocio? (Por favor, elija 5)

Subsidios	
Prohibiciones legales	X
Derechos de uso de la propiedad	
Retirada obligatoria de tierras de explotación	
Compensaciones	X
Bonos verdes	
Pago directo o recompensa por servicios ecosistémicos	X
Responsabilidad social corporativa	
Servidumbres de conservación	
Impuestos y cargos	X
Concesiones de conservación	

Etiquetas de comercialización (certificados/normas de sostenibilidad)	
Etiquetas de comercialización (sin certificados ni normas)	x

P2.4 ¿Considera que en su región hay un gran desarrollo de modelos de negocio que promueven la salud del suelo?

No

P2.5 ¿Cuál considera que es la principal barrera para implementar modelos de negocio que promuevan la salud del suelo?

Falta de políticas para facilitar su implementación		Falta de digitalización del sector	
Falta de información al respecto		Falta de interés por parte de los propietarios	
Falta de recursos económicos		Falta de una agencia de apoyo	
Falta de apreciación por parte del consumidor/sociedad	x	Otro (por favor, especificar)	

P2.6 ¿Considera que las políticas actuales (PAC, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc.) promueven el desarrollo de nuevos modelos de negocio que promueven la salud del suelo?

No. Estas políticas están centradas más en las prácticas agrarias que en los mercados o los modelos de negocio.

P2.7 ¿Debería el sector privado tener un papel predominante en la implementación de los modelos de negocio?

Si. Los modelos de negocio deben nacer de iniciativas privadas o no serán viables en el tiempo.

P2.8 Existen ciertos sectores que pueden tener un mejor potencial para la implementación de modelos de negocio de salud del suelo a través del sector privado? (S/N) Y por favor explique.

Si.

Al menos en el sector agroalimentario, todo lo relacionado con la calidad de los procesos en el sistema productivo, puede trasladarse a la valoración de productos y su puesta en el mercado con valor diferencial.

3) Co-construcción

Por lo general, los impactos y cambios en el suelo tienden a ser a medio y largo plazo por lo que en un modelo de negocio relacionado en salud del suelo, muchos de los impactos suelen tardar varios años en tener efecto.

P3.1 ¿Cuál consideraría que debería ser la duración de un contrato entre la administración pública o inversores privados y propietarios de tierras dentro de un modelo de negocio?

	1 año	2 años	5 años	10 años	20 años
Agricultura				x	
Forestal					
Urbano					

P3.2 Hoy en día, el desarrollo tecnológico en todos los sectores permite monitorizar de forma ágil y "low cost". Si usted era el propietario del terreno, elija una de las siguientes opciones en cada fila:

	Agricultura	Forestal	Urbano
Seguimiento anual con los pagos asociados recibidos (si los hubiera) en un área aleatoria de su parcela.			
El seguimiento anual con pagos asociados (si los hubiera) se realiza siempre en un área previamente especificada			
Seguimiento anual sin pagos asociados para obtener recomendaciones de gestión por parte contratante			
Un análisis al principio del contrato y el otro al final			

Con el fin de diseñar una mejor estrategia para implementar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo en su región, por favor, responda las siguientes preguntas desde su perspectiva.

P3.3 ¿Cuáles son las fortalezas de los propietarios de tierras al adoptar el negocio de la salud del suelo? Esta pregunta tiene como objetivo analizar las fortalezas internas que los propietarios de tierras pueden tener al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo desde una perspectiva empresarial y ambiental.

Apostar por la salud del suelo repercute en la sostenibilidad de la productividad del terreno en el medio plazo. Desintensificar determinadas labores y prácticas de manejo en el suelo, a pesar de una pérdida en el

rendimiento económico, puede verse compensada poniendo en valor estas prácticas conservacionistas de los suelos.

P3.4 ¿Cuáles son las debilidades de los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta examina las debilidades que los propietarios de tierras en general pueden enfrentar al adoptar modelos comerciales de salud del suelo, por ejemplo, falta de información, limitaciones financieras, infraestructura inadecuada, etc..

Es difícil apostar modelos de negocio cuando hasta el momento el mercado no reconoce la salud del suelo. Se necesita avanzar en la concienciación del consumo para que puedan reconocerse atributos productivos relacionadas con manejos que mejoran la salud del suelo.

P3.5 ¿Cuáles son las oportunidades para los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta examina las oportunidades que los propietarios de tierras pueden enfrentar externamente al adoptar modelos de negocios de salud del suelo. Por ejemplo, nuevas herramientas financieras, innovación en productos y nuevas oportunidades de mercado

La oportunidad radica en la oportunidad de mercado que supone mostrar nuevos atributos en productos agroalimentarios procedentes de prácticas agrarias que mejoran y redundan en la salud del suelo.

P3.6 ¿Cuáles son las amenazas para los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta analiza las amenazas para las empresas a la hora de adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo. Esta pregunta requiere información, por ejemplo, relacionada con la difusión de negocios de salud del suelo a nivel nacional / regional. Un ejemplo de amenaza podría ser la falta de interés de los consumidores.

Las amenazas, además de la falta de conciencia en el consumo, son la ausencia de estándares oficiales para el reconocimiento de cuales son las prácticas que mejoran la salud del suelo, y por tanto el riesgo de competencia desleal entre diferentes modelos de negocio que no sean equiparables.

ID: EVENOR07

1) General

Edad	18-29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-39 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 40-49 <input type="checkbox"/>	País ESPAÑA		
	50-59 <input type="checkbox"/> 60-69 <input type="checkbox"/> +70 <input type="checkbox"/>			
Genero	Mujer	Masculino	No binario	Prefiero no responder X
Sector				
Agricultores <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Investigadores <input type="checkbox"/>		Responsable político <input type="checkbox"/>
Industria y cadena de valor <input type="checkbox"/>		Propietario de tierras <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		ONGs y sociedad civil <input type="checkbox"/>
Consumidores <input type="checkbox"/>		Otros <input type="checkbox"/> Especificar:		

P.1.1 ¿Es usted miembro de alguna asociación ambiental (por ejemplo, WWF, otros) y/o participa en acciones financiadas para la protección del medio ambiente?

SI No

P.1.2 ¿Está implementando actualmente alguna actividad comercial de salud del suelo (Marque con una X)?

Cultivo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Ganadería	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Agricultura biológica	<input type="checkbox"/>
Operaciones de invernadero	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agroturismo	<input type="checkbox"/>
Apicultura	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Cultivo de setas	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Cultivo de hierbas	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cultivos especiales (es decir, frutas exóticas)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alquiler de equipos agrícolas	<input type="checkbox"/>
Consultoría de cultivos	<input type="checkbox"/>
Comercialización agrícola	<input type="checkbox"/>
Producción de semillas	<input type="checkbox"/>
Producción de fertilizantes y enmiendas al suelo	<input type="checkbox"/>
Software de gestión agrícola	<input type="checkbox"/>
Financiación agrícola	<input type="checkbox"/>
Seguros agrarios	<input type="checkbox"/>
Producción de madera	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Ordenación forestal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Procesamiento de madera	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fabricación de pulpa y papel	<input type="checkbox"/>
Carpintería y artesanía	<input type="checkbox"/>
Recreación forestal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Manejo de vida silvestre	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Créditos de carbono forestal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Otro: CAZA, PESCA Y USOS RECREATIVOS Y DEPORTIVOS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

P1.3 Si su respuesta fue positiva, ¿cuál es su objetivo de salud del suelo?

Secuestro de carbono orgánico del suelo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Biodiversidad del suelo	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nitrógeno	<input type="checkbox"/>
Estructura del suelo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Otro:

2) Características

Hay tres áreas principales relacionadas con el negocio de la salud del suelo: agricultura, agrosilvicultura y urbano. Cada uno podría tener diferentes objetivos de salud del suelo. Según el último informe de la Agencia Europea de Medio Ambiente, hemos recopilado las variables de salud del suelo objetivo.

P2.1 Por favor, elija cinco amenazas del suelo más relevantes desde su perspectiva en su región (1 más importante, 5 menos importante).

Amenaza del suelo	Indicador	Puntuación
Pérdida de carbono orgánico del suelo		
Cultivo	Caída por debajo del nivel óptimo de carbono orgánico del suelo	5
Pérdida de nutrientes		
Agricultura	Sobrepasar los niveles críticos de nitrógeno mineral (tierras agrícolas)	1
Forestal	Limitación del nitrógeno basada en el exceso de la relación Carbono/Nitrógeno	2
Agricultura	Caída del fósforo por debajo de los niveles óptimos	4
Forestal	Limitación del fósforo basada en el exceso de la relación Nitrógeno/Fósforo	1
Acidificación		
Agricultura	Superación de los niveles críticos de pH (por ejemplo, causada por factores externos)	1
Forestal	Superación de los niveles críticos de Aluminio inorgánico	1
Contaminación del suelo		
Todos los usos del suelo	Superación de los valores de cribado para el riesgo crítico de metales pesados	1

Todos los usos del suelo	Superación de los valores de cribado para el riesgo crítico de contaminantes orgánicos	1
Erosión del suelo		
Agricultura	Superación de la tasa real de pérdida de suelo por erosión hídrica	5
Agricultura	Superación de la tasa real de pérdida de suelo por erosión eólica	5
Pérdida de biodiversidad del suelo		
Pérdida de biodiversidad del suelo (subindicadores)	Exceder las normas mínimas seguras de conservación de los ecosistemas. Exceso de rangos de operación (OR) para animales y microorganismos específicos del suelo	5

El mercado relacionado con la salud del suelo y los bienes que se pueden obtener de él es muy variado. Este amplio abanico de posibilidades en el mercado dificulta la definición de una situación clara.

En el entregable 1.1, hemos categorizado 4 tipos de modelos de negocio relacionados con la salud del suelo en el marco del proyecto NOVASOIL.

P2.2 Desde su perspectiva, por favor, indique su relevancia para mejorar la salud del suelo en su región.

Tipo	Nada relevante	Menos relevante	Medio	Más relevante	Totalmente relevante
Pago por servicios ecosistémicos					X
Cadena de valor				X	
Créditos de carbono					X
Implementación colectiva					X
Otras (Por favor, especificar)					

P2.3 ¿Qué incentivos cree que son los más importantes para estimular la salud del suelo mejorando los modelos de negocio? (Por favor, elija 5)

Subsidios	
Prohibiciones legales	
Derechos de uso de la propiedad	
Retirada obligatoria de tierras de explotación	
Compensaciones	X
Bonos verdes	X
Pago directo o recompensa por servicios ecosistémicos	X
Responsabilidad social corporativa	
Servidumbres de conservación	X
Impuestos y cargos	

Concesiones de conservación	
Etiquetas de comercialización (certificados/normas de sostenibilidad)	
Etiquetas de comercialización (sin certificados ni normas)	

P2.4 ¿Considera que en su región hay un gran desarrollo de modelos de negocio que promueven la salud del suelo? (S/N/Tal vez)

P2.5 ¿Cuál considera que es la principal barrera para implementar modelos de negocio que promuevan la salud del suelo?

Falta de políticas para facilitar su implementación	X	Falta de digitalización del sector	
Falta de información al respecto		Falta de interés por parte de los propietarios	X
Falta de recursos económicos	X	Falta de una agencia de apoyo	
Falta de apreciación por parte del consumidor/sociedad	X	Otro (por favor, especificar)	

P2.6 ¿Considera que las políticas actuales (PAC, Green Deal, NATURA2000, etc.) promueven el desarrollo de nuevos modelos de negocio que promueven la salud del suelo? (S/N) y justificar

En mi region NO promueven nada, la PAC es un simple subsidio, no se perciben los beneficios de la red Natura y no se conoce Green Deal.

P2.7 ¿Debería el sector privado tener un papel predominante en la implementación de los modelos de negocio? (S/N y por qué)

NO, el sector privado no entrará en esto hasta que vea que da beneficios económicos. En la UE los costes son mayores que en países subdesarrollados que es donde se están implementando más estas políticas verdes.

P2.8 Existen ciertos sectores que pueden tener un mejor potencial para la implementación de modelos de negocio de salud del suelo a través del sector privado? (S/N) Y por favor explique.

No tengo una opinion definida acerca de lo que me pregunta.

3) Co-construcción

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	1 año	2 años	5 años	10 años	20 años
Agricultura				x	
Forestal					x
Urbano			x		

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	Agricultura	Forestal	Urbano
Seguimiento anual con los pagos asociados recibidos (si los hubiera) en un área aleatoria de su parcela.	x	x	
El seguimiento anual con pagos asociados (si los hubiera) se realiza siempre en un área previamente especificada	x	x	
Seguimiento anual sin pagos asociados para obtener recomendaciones de gestión por parte contratante			x
Un análisis al principio del contrato y el otro al final			

Con el fin de diseñar una mejor estrategia para implementar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo en su región, por favor, responda las siguientes preguntas desde su perspectiva.

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En mi región hay unas 40.000 ha de tierras reforestadas con los programas europeos de finales de los 90. Atendiendo al Protocolo de Kioto, estas plantaciones serían elegibles para proyectos de absorción. Si a esto le unimos

los posibles créditos de CO2 por fijación en el suelo conseguiríamos una mejora notable del suelo y de las explotaciones.

En estas tierras se dan servicios ecosistémicos tales como apicultura, caza, recolección de setas, producción de esencias de plantas aromáticas y obtención de lambdanum para perfumería, así como caza y pesca deportiva.

P3.4 ¿Cuáles son las debilidades de los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta examina las debilidades que los propietarios de tierras en general pueden enfrentar al adoptar modelos comerciales de salud del suelo, por ejemplo, falta de información, limitaciones financieras, infraestructura inadecuada, etc..

Los propietarios de mi región no invierten nada y tampoco existen incentivos suficientes para incitarlos a invertir. La estructura de la propiedad suele ser: propietarios que mantienen las fincas con ganadería y/o agricultura o son meros rentistas que esperan una oportunidad para vender sus tierras sin hacer nada para que, al menos, mantengan una salud decente.

P3.5 ¿Cuáles son las oportunidades para los propietarios de tierras al adoptar modelos de negocio de salud del suelo? Esta pregunta examina las oportunidades que los propietarios de tierras pueden enfrentar externamente al adoptar modelos de negocios de salud del suelo. Por ejemplo, nuevas herramientas financieras, innovación en productos y nuevas oportunidades de mercado

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El modelo de comercialización de los productos obtenidos no ofrece una retribución justa en comparación con el precio que paga el consumidor.

Additional questionnaires will be found in ZENODO at the end of the project.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y
ID	Age	Country	Gender	Farmers	Researchers	Policy maker	Industry and Landowners	NGOs and ci	Consumers	Others	Others detail	Q1.1	Are you Q1.2	Crop far	Livestock far	Organic farm	Greenhouse / Agritourism	Beekeeping	Mushroom f	Herb farming	Specialty crop	Farm equipm	Crop consult	Agricu
3	EVENDR01	30-39	American Samoa																					
4	EVENDR02	40-49	Netherlands	Male																				
5	EVENDR03	40-49	Spain	Male	1																			
6	EVENDR04	18-29	Kyrgyzstan	Male	1																			
7	EVENDR05	30-39	United Kingdom	Male	1																			
8	EVENDR06	30-39	Serbia	Female	1																			
9	UPM10	18-29	Spain	Female	1																			
10	EVENDR08	30-39	Denmark	Male	1																			
11	UPM09	40-49	Spain	Female	1																			
12	UPM08	40-49	Spain	Female	1																			
13	UPM06	40-49	Spain	Male	1																			
14	UPM01	40-49	Spain	Female	1																			
15	UPM02	40-49	Spain	Male	1																			
16	UPM03	40-49	Spain	No binary	1																			
17	EVENDR12	40-49	Chile	Female	1																			
18	EVENDR13	40-49	Chile	Female	1																			
19	UPM04	40-49	Spain	Male	1																			
20	UPM05	30-39	Spain	Male	1																			
21	EVENDR11	30-39	Spain	Female																				
22	UPM07	30-39	Spain	Female	1																			
23	EVENDR09	30-39	Spain	Male	1																			
24	EVENDR10	40-49	Spain	Male																				
25	EVENDR07	30-39	Spain	Not answer	1																			
26	AREFLH01	40-49	France	Male																				
27	AREFLH02	40-49	France	Female																				
28	AREFLH03	30-39	France	Male																				
29	AREFLH04	40-49	France	Male	1																			
30	AREFLH05	40-49	Spain	Female	1																			
31	AREFLH06	40-49	Spain	Female	1																			
32	AREFLH07	30-39	Spain	Female	1																			
33	AREFLH08	30-39	Italy	Male																				
34	AREFLH09	40-49	Greece	Male	1																			
35	AREFLH10	30-39	Greece	Female	1																			
36	AREFLH11	30-39	Ireland	Male																				
37	AREFLH12	30-39	Greece	Male																				
38	AREFLH13	30-39	Greece	Male																				
39	AREFLH14	30-39	Greece	Male																				
40	AREFLH15	30-39	Spain	Male																				
	ALL	Others	Spain	Latvia	Italy	Germany	Bulgaria	France																